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Stan wiedzy i wyzwania dla lokalizacji opartej na GNSS w lasach

State of art and challenges for GNSS-based locating in forests

Diploma thesis presented to the Faculty of Forestry

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Podsumowanie

Tytuł: Stan wiedzy i wyzwania dla lokalizacji opartej na GNSS w lesie

Lasy odgrywają istotną rolę w naszym ekosystemie i stale się zmieniają. Monitorowanie lasów jest niezbędne, ponieważ technologia teledetekcji znacznie zwiększyła naszą zdolność do obserwowania ich w czasie rzeczywistym. Globalne Systemy Nawigacji Satelitarnej (GNSS) to satelitarne narzędzia do mapowania i pomiaru lasów. Ponieważ systemy nawigacji są stosowane na obszarach leśnych, ich skuteczność może być zagrożona z powodu różnych wyzwań, szczególnie w regionach o gęstej roślinności. Niektóre czynniki przyczyniają się do zmniejszenia dokładności procesów nawigacyjnych w takich warunkach. Niniejszy projekt opiera się na wcześniejszych badaniach terenowych i przeglądach stosowanych technik w celu poprawy dokładności i niezawodności pozycjonowania GNSS w lasach. Zapewnia kompleksowy przegląd technologii GNSS, badając jej podstawowe aspekty, powiązane komponenty i konfigurację operacyjną, szczególnie w połączeniu z technologiami korekcyjnymi stosowanymi w nawigacji. Początkowo projekt koncentruje się na zrozumieniu podstaw GNSS, w tym jego szczegółowej architektury, procedur działania, rodzajów sygnałów, odbiorników i sposobu ich działania. Późniejsze sekcje zagłębiają się w niezawodne techniki GNSS, które zapewniają dokładne pozycjonowanie w środowisku leśnym. Analiza pokazuje, że podczas blokady sygnału, tłumienia i zakłóceń wielościeżkowych dane pozycjonowania można poprawić za pomocą technik rozszerzonych, takich jak kinematyka w czasie rzeczywistym (RTK), różnicowy GNSS (DGNSS) i precyzyjne pozycjonowanie punktu (PPP), przy użyciu technik RTK niektóre wyniki wykazały błąd RMSE 0,0188 m, który jest minimalnym odchyleniem od pierwotnej pozycji, co wskazuje na niezawodność GNSS w nawigacji leśnej. Użytkownicy uzyskali znaczące korzyści z zastosowania tych technik korekcji podczas mapowania w lesie. Zaobserwowano, że integracja zewnętrznej korekcji ze sprzętu i oprogramowania dodatkowo poprawia ogólną dokładność.

Słowa kluczowe: GNSS, wielościeżkowość, rozszerzenie, RTK, DGNSS.

Summary

Title: State of art and challenges for GNSS-based locating in forest

Forests play a vital role in our ecosystem and are constantly changing. Monitoring forests is essential, as remote sensing technology has significantly enhanced our ability to observe them in real-time. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) are satellite-based forest mapping and surveying tools. As navigation systems are applied in forested areas, their effectiveness can be compromised due to various challenges, particularly in regions with dense vegetation. Some

factors contribute to the reduced accuracy of navigation processes in these settings. This project builds on previous field studies and reviews of applied techniques to improve the accuracy and reliability of GNSS positioning in forests. It provides a comprehensive overview of GNSS technology, exploring its fundamental aspects, associated components, and operational setup, particularly in conjunction with correction technologies used in navigation. The project's initial focus is on understanding the fundamentals of GNSS, including its detailed architecture, functioning procedures, types of signals, receivers, and how they operate. The later sections delve into dependable GNSS techniques that yield accurate positioning within forest environments. The analysis reveals that during signal blockage, attenuation, and multipath interference periods, positioning data can be enhanced through augmentation techniques such as Real-Time Kinematics (RTK), Differential GNSS(DGNSS), and Precise Point Positioning (PPP), using RTK techniques some results were showing 0.0188 m RMSE error which is minimum deviation from original position showing GNSS reliability in forestry navigation. Users have gained significant advantages from employing these correction techniques that while mapping in forest. It has been observed that integrating external correction from hardware and software further improves overall accuracy.

Keywords: GNSS, Multipath, Augmentation, RTK, DGNSS.

Zusammenfassung

Titel: Stand der Technik und Herausforderungen für die GNSS-basierte Ortung im Wald

Wälder spielen eine wichtige Rolle in unserem Ökosystem und verändern sich ständig. Die Überwachung der Wälder ist von entscheidender Bedeutung, da die Fernerkundungstechnologie unsere Möglichkeiten, sie in Echtzeit zu beobachten, erheblich verbessert hat. Globale Satellitennavigationssysteme (GNSS) sind satellitengestützte Waldkartierungs- und Vermessungsinstrumente. Da Navigationssysteme in bewaldeten Gebieten eingesetzt werden, kann ihre Wirksamkeit aufgrund verschiedener Probleme beeinträchtigt werden, insbesondere in Regionen mit dichter Vegetation. Einige Faktoren tragen dazu bei, dass die Genauigkeit von Navigationsverfahren in diesen Gebieten abnimmt. Dieses Projekt baut auf früheren Feldstudien und Übersichten über angewandte Techniken zur Verbesserung der Genauigkeit und Zuverlässigkeit der GNSS-Positionierung in Wäldern auf. Es bietet einen umfassenden Überblick über die GNSS-Technologie und untersucht ihre grundlegenden Aspekte, die zugehörigen Komponenten und den Betriebsaufbau, insbesondere in Verbindung mit den in der Navigation verwendeten Korrekturtechniken. Der Schwerpunkt des Projekts liegt zunächst auf dem Verständnis der Grundlagen von GNSS, einschließlich der

detaillierten Architektur, der Funktionsweise, der Signaltypen, der Empfänger und ihrer Funktionsweise. Die späteren Abschnitte befassen sich mit zuverlässigen GNSS-Techniken, die eine genaue Positionsbestimmung in Waldgebieten ermöglichen. Die Analyse zeigt, dass in Zeiten von Signalblockaden, -abschwächungen und Mehrweginterferenzen die Positionsdaten durch Augmentierungstechniken wie Real-Time Kinematics (RTK), Differential GNSS (DGNSS) und Precise Point Positioning (PPP) verbessert werden können. Bei der Verwendung von RTK-Techniken zeigten einige Ergebnisse einen RMSE-Fehler von 0,0188 m, was eine minimale Abweichung von der ursprünglichen Position darstellt und die Zuverlässigkeit von GNSS in der forstwirtschaftlichen Navigation belegt. Die Anwender haben durch den Einsatz dieser Korrekturtechniken bei der Kartierung im Wald erhebliche Vorteile gewonnen. Es wurde festgestellt, dass die Integration der externen Korrektur durch Hardware und Software die Gesamtgenauigkeit weiter verbessert.

Schlüsselwörter: GNSS, Mehrweg, Augmentation, RTK, DGNSS.

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1. Introduction

Forests are broad and complex ecosystems [1], which provide essential support to all living organisms, including humans; they consist of dense trees, bushes, leaves, foliage, and different vegetation, which give energy sources as food and habitat as shelter [2], for all types of species living in its entire ecosystem. The forest can be divided into multiple types of categories location, based on the variation of tree species, geography, and the different climate zones, which can commonly be called ecosystem [3]. Overall, forests provide crucial ecosystem services such as climate control, soil stabilization, and water filtering. Moreover, it provides raw materials such as timber and wood as necessary resources [4], humans have been very dependent upon the forests considered as an income source, where forest economic activity takes place, where the forest has suffered from deforestation and exploitation [5]. In recent practice, it has been seen that forests have suffered stress and threat from human activities due to overuse and deforestation [6]. The protection of the forest seems to be crucial because of illicit harvesting and climate-related stress that includes forest loss. The importance of monitoring and preservation of forests is seen as vital for intervention such practices in the forest [7].

For forests, monitoring and navigation need robust technology that can be used for real-time monitoring. The nature of the forest and its constituents is always changing, and measuring forest with a certain level degree of accuracy is uncertain [8] due to their diverse compositions and huge spatial width. This diverse richness of forests presents significant challenges in accurately measuring features like tree positions and heights. Even logging in the physical location of trees, measurement can be difficult due to weaker satellite communications under dense canopies [9]. Recently, with the use of multiple satellite networks of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) [10], techniques have been used for vivid mapping and monitoring in the forest with navigation tools that provide correct geospatial data [10], allowing accurate mapping and positioning on forest territory. The Global Positioning System (GPS) / GNSS tool has drawn the interest of surveyors or researchers who want to calculate the study area and track and monitor the health status of tree species or entire forest zones. As stated, dense canopy, towering canopies height, rugged

terrain [11] are the barriers that make satellite monitoring cumbersome to gain correct locations. To excel those challenges, there exist already a correction technique [9] that changes the signaling issue and improves the positional accuracy during the navigation of the forest. The literature review aims to evaluate the previously conducted experiment on GNSS located in multiple forest zones and geographical structures and aims to establish a connection bridge between satellite-based navigation and GNSS performance during the study period and correction approaches utilized to obtain the result.

1.1.Importance of Systematic Literature Reviews

The primary objective of a literature review is to have a deep understanding of the challenges present in science and on its various disciplines, thereby minimizing biases in research. As noted by the author [12], diverse resources—including articles, journals, manuscripts, seminar papers, and publications—represent the current landscape of knowledge derived from scientific discoveries, thereby showcasing contemporary findings and practices.

These reviews enable the author to effectively convey insights to the target audience by synthesizing information from a broad range of sources within the scientific community. By implementing a well-structured search strategy, researchers can identify patterns, trends, and gaps in existing literature. When the author diligently follows the established protocol concerning population, intervention, outcomes, and context, they can standardize fundamental components of research pillars to formulate precise research questions.

1.2.Research Objective

The main goal of this research is to understand the various types of problems GNSS faces while located in the forest. Forest measurements are crucial for ensuring accuracy and precision in determining coordinates. Research has shown that various parameters, such as tree height, crown dimensions, and the proximity of surrounding structures, including stand density and other elements of the forest environment, can significantly impact positional error. Setting up the reference station in the survey area can help to test GPS measurements

by providing accurate location data within the forest zones for users, navigators, and researchers [13].

For this research, the main objective is to further refine specific sub-questions:

- i) What strategies are employed to enhance the accuracy and reliability of GNSS in dense forest environments?
- ii) Which methods prove to be the most effective in forest settings?
- iii) What current approaches are utilized for correcting and improving accuracy based on recent trends?

1.3.Review of literature

This chapter provides a technical overview of the fundamentals of GNSS, its satellite constellation, working mechanism, receiver, augmentation types, error or noise, and correction techniques. The later review explains GNSS when introduced in the forest setting and tries to address positioning errors, signal behavior during forest monitoring, and accuracy improvement techniques.

CHAPTER 1

2. Fundamentals of GNSS

"GNSS" refers to a network of combined satellite navigation systems designed for monitoring, mapping, and positioning. These systems developed in various countries and used in daily life practices such as monitoring, mapping, and tracking. Their practical applications are evident in our day-to-day lives, from using GPS for navigation monitoring in forests and weather patterns [14].The GNSS operates on the principle of positioning techniques, where signals are transmitted from multiple satellites to the receiver at a specific distance, as the receiver uses those signals to determine the object's position. The GNSS constellation comprises three segments: namely, **space segment**, **control segment**, and **user**

segment. It has a shared network framework for signal broadcasting and positioning that covers the globe with multilayer coverage. It also broadcasts satellite radio signals related to the satellite's position and time. Navigation satellites serve comparable functions but are uniquely designed to operate at different times based on their intended coverage areas and launch locations [15]. It works in three metrics for system reliability and usability, which are supported by three segments of GNSS [16].

a) Continuity

It is the process of smoothly flowing signal messages to the user without signal discontinuity. It utilizes a multi-constellation navigation network of GNSS to optimize benefits in areas with inadequate infrastructure by enhancing navigation tools in both global and remote regions. The augmentation is an assistant tool that provides consistent coverage of signals over large areas without satellite signal interruptions. It supports navigation and various forest applications like mapping and positioning, particularly in forestry and maritime transport, where precise positioning is crucial for route planning.

b) Accuracy

In the context of (GNSS), accuracy refers to how closely the position derived from GNSS matches the true or actual position. For correct positioning, multiple factors influence accuracy, including clock discrepancies, satellite geometry, and atmospheric propagation errors. These inaccuracies can negatively impact receiver performance during the positioning process. To address these issues, various error reduction techniques applied at either the space-based or ground-based level. Using those mitigating additional tools, the positioning of GNSS utilized by users to improve accuracy to the specific scale.

c) Integrity

It plays a vital role in safety applications like navigation, where the reliability of GNSS is concerned; the various environmental factors like atmospheric disturbance and multipath effects lead to signal interruption and reflection, causing errors in the signaling data. The

integrity of the monitoring system is used to continuously access the GNSS signal that provides vigilant and warnings to the user for inaccurate and unreliable data. Such investigation makes users perceptive, particularly in the field of satellite navigation, receiving reliable information, or promptly warning for potential dangers of incorrect data that are likely to happen.

Space Segment: The space segment of GNSS includes four minimum satellite constellations visible from any location on the Earth. Their primary role is to transmit coded signals for timing, distance, and navigation data for satellite position and time correction using the satellite clock.

Control Segment: The control segment performs various tasks, including tracking satellites and estimating the onboard clock state for broadcasting. It defines the path of each satellite for generating almanac data, which consists of satellite positions and the status of primary orbital information. It can also predict with the ephemeris, which is related to the control segment that provides information on the orbit of individual satellites for a specific time whereby using almanac and ephemeris data, GNSS enhances accuracy and in satellite navigation and allows orbit correction and system performance [16].

User segment: The user segment comprises of the receiver and its associated components, which collaboratively function to compute navigation equations necessary for determining an object's positional coordinates. This segment is crucial in translating satellite signals into actionable spatial data, enabling accurate positioning and navigation capabilities across various applications.

2.1. GPS

The first positioning satellite operated by the United States is a member of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) constellation, which consists of three segments.

- a) **Space Segment:** The space segment is vital in providing precise positioning data in artificial satellite navigation. Since GPS is a member associate of the GNSS

constellation, the space segment consists of twenty-four active satellites arranged on six orbits, having four additional supplementary satellites on every orbit that enhance reliability and increase coverage. Each active satellite broadcasts radio signals that include a distinctive code.

Figure 1: GPS -24 Satellite Configuration [17].

b) Control Segments

It comprises a network of ground-based infrastructures consisting of ground antennas, monitoring stations, and control centers. The control segment manages and maintains the system's operation by tracking and evaluating satellite signals, transmits commands and data updates to the GPS constellation, and revises navigation messages to ensure accurate positioning.

c) User Segments

This segment consists of devices that use satellite signals from GNSS (i.e. GPS, GLONASS, Galileo and Beidou) for monitoring, positioning and timing with the help of satellite signals that operating through various receivers and antennas. The transmitted signals from the satellite are assigned within the L band signals, with the frequencies L1 and L2 having 1575.42 MHz and 1227.60 MHz. Those signals are processed by users like navigators, sailors, military personnel, and common people, collectively called users. The user segment is equipped with GNSS receivers that can provide multiple services like satellite tracking, interacting with satellite signal health from corresponding orbit, and performing signal propagation by traveling signals in the atmosphere and time measurements.

Figure 2: GNSS 3 Segments [18].

CHAPTER 2

2.2. Satellite Orbit Fundamental

An orbit is a path followed by a satellite in space. The satellite where it moves is called the Orbital plane. The orbital angle is made from the earth's equatorial and satellite planes. An inclined orbit occurs when the inclination angle of the satellite is 90° . For any satellite, it completes its one full orbit around the Earth in one orbital period. To achieve this orbit, navigation satellites are launched, placed directly in orbit, given free fall due to gravitation pulls from the Earth, and the satellite goes missing because of the Earth's slight perturbation caused by Earth's rotation, causing deviation from the original path. The motion of those deviated satellites can be assumed by the Keplerian law of movement [14, 19].

Figure 3: Orbital Geometry [20]

2.2.1 Kepler's three laws:

Satellites in orbits travel around the Earth along elliptical paths, with the Earth located at one of the ellipse's foci. As a satellite moves along this path, its speed changes, and it moves faster when closer to Earth and slower when farther away, ensuring that it sweeps out equal areas in equal time intervals. Moreover, the square of a satellite's orbital period is directly proportional to the cube of its average distance from Earth.

2.2.2 Orbit shape determination.

In the context of GNSS, orbit shape determination helps with accurate positioning, satellite geometry, and the time of satellite signal, which allows for precise navigation and positioning. Orbit error correction also helps with accurate orbital data that ensures data reliability. The multiple parameters associate orbit, as the eccentricity parameter of the satellite used to describe the shape as (e) and the radius as (r) concerning the difference between the sum of apogee(r_a) and perigee (r_p), where perigee (r_p) is the point in the satellite's Orbit which is close to Earth whereas apogee(r_a) is the farthest point from the Earth that represents the semi-major axis.

The governing equation for the difference to the sum of apogee,

$$e = (r_a - r_p) / (r_a + r_p) \text{ -----i)}$$

Radius at perigee (r_p)

$$r_p = a (1 - e) \text{ -----ii)}$$

Radius at apogee (r_a),

$$r_p = a (1 + e) \text{ -----iii)}$$

As both perigee and apogee are measured on Earth's center with the radius (r_E) which is equal to 6378 km for the apogee height given by

$$h_a = r_p - r_E \text{ -----iv)}$$

Combination of zero eccentricity

When (e) of an orbit is equal to zero, then (r_a) distance and (r_p) are equal, where the satellites maintain a constant distance from the Earth's center through the orbit.

(e) = 0 in the perfect circular orbit, i.e.,

In the circular orbit, radius to apogee and radius to perigee are equal to a semi-major axis (a)

$$r_a = r_p = a$$

Altering the altitude of a satellite in a circular orbit can influence the duration of its complete orbit. In this context, it is known as a sidereal day when the Earth completes one full rotation (360°) relative to the stars in approximately 23 hours, 56 minutes, and 4.091 seconds. To achieve a geosynchronous orbit, a satellite must maintain an inclination angle of zero and position itself within a geostationary orbit, following a circular path. The orbital period can differ among satellites, even those in similar elliptical orbits, due to various factors such as the Earth's asymmetry and the gravitational effects of the Moon and the Sun.

2.2.3 Types of Satellite Orbits

The commonly used orbits for satellites are the Low-Earth Orbit (LEO), Medium-Earth Orbit (MEO), and Geosynchronous Earth Orbit (GEO).

a) LEO

Satellites orbiting in LEO are the most common ones used for satellite navigation. They are in low positions in the orbital configuration and require a higher amount of velocity to be stabilized on their orbit path. The LEO orbits are situated closer to the Earth, where signal loss transmission is minimal. Being located on the lower orbit, it has better surface transmission or path loss that provides monitoring as well as communication. Each LEO

satellite is up to 40 kilometers closer compared to the Geo satellite, offering less communication delay because less amount of time is required for transmission of the signal [21].

b) MEO

MEO satellite orbits are positioned from 10,000 to 25,000 km from the earth's surface and have an orbital period of 6-12 hours. They provide a broader range of transmission than LEO, which makes global communication possible. Typically, MEO satellites follow polar orbits, enabling coverage across all latitudes, including high-latitude areas, which are crucial for navigation for GNSS satellites. The Polar orientation orbits open, ensuring global coverage even in remote locations as satellites pass with Earth's rotation [22].

c) GEO

The Geo satellites are located at an altitude of 35,856 km in a fixed orbit, where they maintain a balance between gravitational and necessary orbital velocity to remain in a circular path above the equator. Those satellites have zero eccentricity, and their orbits are perfectly circular. While some geostationary satellites are part of SAB to enhance navigation accuracy, not all geo-stationary satellites are interconnected with this framework. Each satellite has an orbital period that is around 23 hours, 56 minutes, and 4 seconds, allowing it to remain synchronized with the earth's rotation, effectively appearing stationary relative to specific points on the surface [17, 23].

2.2.4 Perturbation on Orbit

As the Earth is not a perfect sphere, irregular shape, size, and uneven mass distribution affect satellite orbits. The numerous parameters that take on the satellite and cause perturbation in the orbit are gravitational attractions from celestial bodies that cause various effects. The

spherical harmonic coefficient represents the differences in gravitational potential across multiple regions of the Earth, illustrating specific aspects of the planet's gravitational irregularities and the Earth's gravitational field that have a considerable effect on the determination of location on the unsettling tidal characteristics of the earth along its ocean [24]. Similarly, with their gravity force, various celestial bodies, the sun and the moon, influence orbit [13].

2.2.5 Atmospheric drag

The multiple factors responsible for changes in the artificial satellite on its orbital effect are satellite's mass, surface area, and atmospheric density. As artificial satellites possess smaller mass comparatively than celestial bodies like the moon and other planets, the small navigation satellites are impacted significantly by the atmospheric drag, which comes from atmospheric particles of high altitudes, as those particles create the friction that is responsible for diminishing satellites' orbital energy which declines height and changes in the motion of the satellite [16]. Similarly, larger celestial bodies, including the sun and moon, have their gravitational pull and are directly responsible for the effect on the orbit's shape of the satellite. When their strength is calculated, those forces exert a specific effect on the satellite. In the vacuum, all celestial bodies travel in the atmosphere and experience atmospheric friction, where atmospheric density has some influence on the orbital motion of their bodies. These disturbing forces are responsible for creating challenges for the stability of satellite orbit [13]. As a result, satellite orbit affects GNSS signal wave quality.

CHAPTER 3

2.3. Signal and Receiver

GNSS wavelengths are electromagnetic waves transmitted by satellites to receivers. They operate on three leading bands: L1, L2, and L5, with the corresponding frequencies of 1575.42 MHz, 1227.60 MHz, and 1176.45 MHz, respectively. All receivers can receive L1 signals, predominantly transmitted by GNSS navigation satellites, while some receivers can

also pick up both L1 and L2 signals. Certain GPS receivers can operate across all three frequencies, whereas most GPS systems widely broadcast L1 signals.

Figure 4: Basic overview of GPS receiver [25]

a) GPS signal composition

It includes three main components that consist of a carrier signal, PRN codes, also known as (Pseudo-Random Noise), and a navigation message. The carrier signal is a sinusoidal wave with a unique frequency that transmits PRN Codes and navigation messages. The carrier signal contains no specific data, whereas each satellite's PRN code is unique. The codes are specifically designed to minimize misinterpretation and resemblance, making it extremely difficult for others to misrepresent them. Each satellite generates a unique code for its identification. The PRN Codes are broadcast continuously and are constantly repeated. To

receive messages from individual satellites, each unique code acts as a key that enables the receiver operator to unlock the corresponding satellite's message. In the context of GPS, navigation messages encompass a diverse set of data critical for positioning, including Keplerian parameters, orbital inclination, satellite clock updates, ephemeris data, and the health status of individual satellites. Furthermore, these messages convey vital information regarding the satellite's position, the time at which the message was generated, and the timestamp of the data's release. Collectively, the navigation message facilitates the accurate determination of the satellite's orbital position [17].

Figure 5 : GPS L1 signal and process of modulation [17].

b) GPS Frequencies/Radio frequency (RF)

The signal processing in RF systems encompasses a combination of digital and analog circuits. The receivers employ various sophisticated techniques for signal processing, including code correlation, code phase detection, and frequency acquisition. These advanced methods process the signal and facilitate carrier signal multiplication of transmitted data. A receiver consists of several channels, which are communication paths for receiving and tracking data from the satellite to the receiver, containing valuable messages. Three principal techniques are adopted to receive radio frequency (RF) for tracking GPS signals. The receivers exhibit differences in performance, falling into different categories based on their

diverse ranges and functionalities. The L1 signal PRN codes consist of the P-code, Y-code, and C/A codes, signal structures transmitted from GNSS satellites [25].

The P and Y Codes are reserved for military and security applications, while the C/A code is transmitted on L1 frequency (1575.45 MHz for common people). The P-code is broadcast on L1 and L2 frequencies for security personnel and authorized users, and the Y-code, which is an encrypted version of the P-code, is transmitted as dual-frequency transmission for better positional accuracy.

Figure 6 : PRN code with the carrier signal [14]

c) GPS Antenna

The GPS antenna receives electromagnetic signals transmitted from satellites to the receivers. After receiving those signals, they are converted into electrical signals at radio frequency (RF) with the help of the receiver's antenna. As the signals originate from satellites located approximately 20,000 km away, antennas are designed to be highly sensitive to receiving distant signals [26], having the facility for optimization. They can operate within specific bandwidths for their intended functions, with higher bands offering greater opportunities for improved performance and higher positioning accuracy. The stability and positioning of antennas can be assessed by calculating the phase center, which represents the physical center of the antenna's location. A tripod stand needs to be fixed where a tripod is strategically placed at this survey center of the plot or area to determine its coordinates. The antenna gain pattern denotes the receiver's capability to capture signals at different azimuthal (horizontal)

and elevational (vertical) angles. Antennas effectively track signals at low elevations across all azimuths [33].

d) Front end

The front end is the part of the receiver antenna responsible for completing various tasks, including signal processing, which involves different operations depending on the type of receiver. Raw data received from antennas typically contains a significant amount of noise that must be addressed through amplification and removal using a front-end filter. Here, the amplification of satellite signals consists of weak signals and noise to detect weak satellite signals effectively. Subsequently, the amplified noise is converted down to a lower frequency by front-end designers. The desired signal is then digitized through an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and converted into a bit format. To minimize the signal loss, higher bit numbers are utilized. The governing equation for this entire process is given by,

$$K = L/\sigma \dots\dots\dots i)$$

In this process, automatic gain control (AGC) is utilized to adjust the power of the signal, while K represents the optimal ratio for improving signal to noise ratio, 'L' represents signal length, and 'σ' the standard deviation of the noise level [27].

e) Baseband Processing

Baseband processing consists of two primary operations: acquisition and tracking. In the acquisition stage, the GPS receiver utilizes the CDMA (Code Division Multiple Access), where all satellites broadcast on the same frequency with different codes. They differentiate signals from different satellites, and receivers generate local copies of PRN codes and compare them with incoming signals. These locally produced codes are shifted forward and backwards while being compared with the signals. When the signals exhibit a similar nature, they are considered highly correlated. By evaluating the movement of the local copy

concerning the incoming signals, during travel, the (Δt) time delay can be determined. The time delay describes the delay between a satellite transmitting a signal and the GPS receiver receiving that signal. This process takes place in a 2-D search space, where the receiver calculates the pseudo-range, speed of light and delayed time, where the estimated distance of the satellite can be computed. Additionally, estimates for Doppler shift and various signal delays can be made. In the tracking stage, the Delay Lock Loop (DLL) and Phase Lock Loop (PLL) are also employed for two purposes. DLL is responsible for code phase synchronization, while PLL handles carrier phase synchronization. Both together synchronize the locally generated signals to the receiver, updating calculation for any movements or changes in the process of signals during the positioning process [15].

f) Pseudorange-Based Algorithm

In the GNSS positioning, pseudo-range (R) is the apparent distance between satellites and the GNSS receiver, which is affected by the receivers' clock bias. This bias arises due to the receiver's internal clock, which is not perfectly synchronized with the satellite clocks. The pseudo-range is determined by measuring the time difference between the signal emission time from the satellite to the reception time of the receiver. The emission time can be achieved by calculating clock bias with the speed of light relating to the time difference of the pseudo-range, for calculation of pseudo-range, travel the receiver signal time, c speed of light and that the satellite time signal transmission and Δt representing difference time in receiver clock bias.

$$R = c (t_{\text{rcv}}[\text{reception}] - t_{\text{sat}}[\text{emission}])$$

Signal emission time, measured from a satellite clock (t_{sat}), given by

$$t_{\text{sat}} [\text{emission}] = t_{\text{rcv}}[\text{reception}] - \Delta t$$

where $\Delta t = R/c$, where c denotes the speed of light [28]

g) Doppler shift

The Doppler effect refers to the change in the carrier wave frequency caused by the disparity in the motion of the satellite with the receiver. This leads to a Doppler shift, which denotes a change in the observed frequency of the signal received and the frequency of the sources. For example, the frequency of the primary source for L1 is 1575.42, L2 is 1227.60, and L5 equals 1176.45 units in MHz.

Doppler equation: $f_R = f_T \left(1 - \frac{\dot{r}}{v_s}\right)$, Where \dot{r} represents range rate, λ as signal wavelength, v_s represents the velocity of the source, f_R and f_T representing received frequency and transmitted frequency. The rearrangement of the equation is given as, $(f_R - f_T) = -\frac{\dot{r}}{\lambda}$ [14]

CHAPTER 4

2.4. Trilateration

The principles of GNSS are based on trilateration, a method that involves determining an unknown position by measuring distances from multiple satellite locations. These distances are calculated using the time that it takes for signals to travel from the satellites, multiplied by the speed of light. Based on this, the receiver's position is pinpointed as the center of spheres with radii equal to the calculated distances. This method delivers coordinates with meter-level accuracy under standard conditions.

Figure 7: Position computation by trilateration sources [29]

By utilizing the established coordinates, the control points, the additional control points, and the reference points, accurate distances can be measured. The trilateration technique is employed to determine the relative positions of an unknown location based on the distances measured from at least three reference points in 2D plane and four reference points in 3D space. This involves measuring the distance between the subject and each reference point to ascertain the correct position accurately. While trilateration for space navigation typically uses three reference points to determine a position on a 2D plane, four reference points are required for accurate 3D trilateration. This is because three reference points create three spheres whose intersections can yield two possible locations, one of which is often invalid (located underground). Adding a fourth reference point ensures that the position can be uniquely determined in three-dimensional space and helps correct for potential timing errors caused by variations in satellite clocks or atmospheric conditions. In GNSS, the receiver clock bias is consistent across all measurements, resulting in a common bias for the position coordinates (x, y, z) and the receiver's clock bias (t) that must be resolved for accurate positioning if slight timing difference leading more significant error in distance calculation that ensure acute timing essential to resolve receiver clock bias and to reflect true location of the receiver.

$\rho = R + ct$ -----i) receiver - clock-biased range, also called pseudo-range

where c is the velocity of light, t is the receiver clock error, ρ is the measured pseudo-range, and R is the geometric range.

$$R^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \text{ -----ii)}$$

$$R^2 = (x_r - x_s)^2 + (y_r - y_s)^2 + (z_r - z_s)^2 \text{ -----iii)}$$

$$R = \sqrt{((x_r - x_s)^2 + (y_r - y_s)^2 + (z_r - z_s)^2)} \text{ -----iv)}$$

Where x_s, y_s, z_s are satellite's coordinate points and x_r, y_r, z_r are the receiver's coordinate points for each observation. The equation mentioned calculates the geometric distance between the GNSS satellite and receiver and determines receiver positioning using trilateration.

$$\rho = \sqrt{((x_r - x_s)^2 + (y_r - y_s)^2 + (z_r - z_s)^2)} + c \cdot t \text{ -----v)}$$

For all four satellites, the generalized equation is as follows,

$$\rho_1 = \sqrt{((x_r - x_1)^2 + (y_r - y_1)^2 + (z_r - z_1)^2)} + c \cdot t \text{ -----vi)}$$

$$\rho_2 = \sqrt{((x_r - x_2)^2 + (y_r - y_2)^2 + (z_r - z_2)^2)} + c \cdot t \text{ -----vii)}$$

$$\rho_3 = \sqrt{((x_r - x_3)^2 + (y_r - y_3)^2 + (z_r - z_3)^2)} + c \cdot t \text{ -----viii)}$$

$$\rho_4 = \sqrt{((x_r - x_4)^2 + (y_r - y_4)^2 + (z_r - z_4)^2)} + c \cdot t \text{ -----ix)}$$

where (x_1, y_1, z_1) , (x_2, y_2, z_2) , (x_3, y_3, z_3) , and (x_4, y_4, z_4) are the location of four satellites, and $\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3,$ and ρ_4 denote the pseudo-range of the satellites from the receiver's position. The given equations i-iv) are used for determining the receiver's precise position and the relationship between pseudo-range measurement from satellites to unknown receiver position and clock bias, a fundamental process in GNSS positioning.

2.5. Satellite requirements for positioning

In the context of terrestrial positioning, every satellite appears on the horizon for effective signaling. It can be understood that the plane cannot intersect the earth, for 3-D positioning, a minimum of four satellites are needed, where three satellites determine positioning, whereas fourth satellite resolves the timing discrepancies in the receiver clock as well as provides information about altitude to pinpoint the exact location for accurate and precision of the object. Even though four satellites are enough for accurate positioning, however, in forest zone more than four satellites are needed to produce better results due to low signals [13].

Figure 8: GNSS positioning with reference to four satellites [13].

2.6. Dilution of Precision

The most important component for the accurate determination of an object from the satellite's position, which depends upon the distribution of the satellite during the observation period, directly impacts the positioning quality. The dilution level is a numeric representation of the precision level in the accuracy of the satellite's position based on geometrical alignment [20].

A lower dilution is better for positioning accuracy. A larger number of satellites does not necessarily provide better positioning, but their proper alignment is a more prominent factor

in the higher accuracy projection. During navigation of the object, when satellites are well spread over and are located higher in horizon, those alignment are more favorable and have low variance with greater positional precision [19]. A higher confidence level indicates greater precision. Better satellite geometry and lower DOP are associated with a larger spatial volume defined by lines connecting the receiver device to the satellites. This value communicates the satellite's geometric state to the user, particularly concerning the horizon. Numerous types of precision dilution are classified based on geometric, positional, horizontal, vertical, and temporal, explaining how satellite geometry affects accuracy across different dimensions [15].

2.6.1 HDOP (Horizontal Dilution of Precision)

HDOP is a metric that refers to satellite geometry used for horizontal positional measurement, particularly concerning latitude and longitude. It provides critical information regarding the relative arrangement of satellites in the sky and their influence on the accuracy of horizontal position measurements. A lower HDOP value indicates better satellite geometry and improved positional accuracy. The underlined equation represents the horizontal direction error,

$$\text{HDOP} = \sqrt{(\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2)} \text{ or } \sqrt{(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2)}$$

Here σ_E , σ_N , error in the east and north direction, with a similar representation of σ_x and σ_y , x-axis and y-axis on co-ordinate.

2.6.2 VDOP (Vertical Dilution of Precision)

The VDOP refers to satellite geometry used for vertical positional measurement, particularly altitude. It provides critical information regarding the relative arrangement of satellites in the sky and their influence on vertical positioning accuracy.

VDOP = $\sqrt{(\sigma_h^2)}$ or $\sqrt{(\sigma_z^2)}$, when horizontal dilution and vertical dilution are combined, the uncertainty of position error can be calculated, called Positional Dilution of

Precision(PDOP). In the same way, the receiver clock's inconsistency concerning the time-related measurement of satellite position in the sky provides information about the effect of timing on the accuracy of the objects during positioning, which can be calculated by Time Dilution Of Precision (TDOP) and represented as $\sqrt{(\sigma_T^2)}$. In the same way, other essential factors expressing the satellite's geometrical alignment in the sky and their impact during the positioning can be obtained from the geometric dilution of precision, which is represented as GDOP, that can be calculated collectively as a combination of all DOP, i.e., HDOP, VDOP, and TDOP, states about geometric alignment pattern of the satellite that affects the accuracy during the time of measurement. The equation of GDOP can be calculated as $\sqrt{(\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2 + \sigma_h^2 + \sigma_T^2)}$ or $GDOP = \sqrt{(PDOP^2 + TDOP^2)}$. It is a measurement error from the satellite position to the receiver position.

Figure 9 : Positioning alignment of satellites a) poor b) good geometry [19]

CHAPTER 5

2.7. Sources of errors during navigation

Various factors influence GNSS signals, some dependent on the user and others user independent. The user-dependent factors encompass technical errors, receiver settings, and equipment malfunctions. In contrast, independent factors arise from the ionosphere and Earth's environment—elements that lie beyond human control and are constantly in flux, resulting in potential inaccuracies. These errors can generally be categorized into three groups: satellite-based, signal transmission, and receiver-based.

2.7.1 Clock Errors

The nature of the GNSS clock is stable, with low ability for perfect synchronization, and it records the actual time of satellite navigation through its internal atomic clock. The clock error means the deviation of the time margin between the actual time and the true time that affects the accuracy of the positioning data [16]. Its occurring factors are mainly clocking drift, relativistic effect, environmental influence and probably aging. These factors create a major drawback for accuracy positioning in the field of navigation. To address timing issues, GNSS systems timely send information on the correction data on the issues like clock drift , ageing to ensure more accurate positioning [13].

2.7.2 Satellite Clock Drift

It is the deviation of the satellites' onboard atomic clock from its real-time due to predictable and random factors. For predictable factor aging, clock bias, and relativistic factors where satellite clock timing faster than earth's clock time are responsible, whereas random factors

like noise and radiation effects are responsible [16].The satellite's atomic clocks are built precisely for time deliverance. GNSS regulates clock data correction from the monitoring station to the satellite for these errors. As these clocks are monitored from ground stations, correction terms and conditions for error are enclosed in the message, and corrections are broadcast in the navigation message of the satellite [22].

2.7.3 Atmospheric Error (Ionosphere, Troposphere)

As the satellite signal travels through the Earth's atmosphere, it encounters various mediums, leading to a reduction in speed and deviation from its original path by the time it reaches the receiver [30].Upon entering the Earth's atmosphere, the signal interacts with different layers of the ionosphere, where scattering medium with varying electron density, causing the electromagnetic waves to refract and resulting in a longer signal run time, consequently altering the speed[31].The equation of ionospheric effect,

$$v = (40.3 / (c \cdot f^2)) \text{ TEC}$$

Where v is the ionospheric delay, c is the speed of light in m/s, f is the signal frequency in Hz, and total electron content (TEC) constant unit , used for the free electrons per cubic meter [13].

2.7.4 Ionospheric Error

The ionosphere is part of the Earth's atmosphere that extends from 50 km to 1000 km above the Earth's surface. It influences the behavior of signals from the sun and comprises several layers. GNSS signals are mainly affected in this region, resulting in group or phase delays. The magnitude of these delays determines the density and thickness of the layer. The nature of ionospheric delay fluctuates and varies under different conditions such as morning to evening, heat, time, weather, and seasons. The ionospheric effect differs from the poles to the equator and causes a delay in all modulation codes, also known as group delay. This delay ranges from a few meters to twenty meters and is influenced by complex physical interactions due to geomagnetic fields, solar processes, and frequency[16, 32].

Figure 10: Ionospheric error during the signal transmission [17]

2.7.5 Tropospheric Errors

Errors occurring in the troposphere, which is situated above the earth's surface, are generally caused by refraction in the troposphere. The stratosphere is the electrically neutral layer where ionization and neutralization do not impact radio signals. Refraction of all GNSS frequencies occurs on the troposphere, causing the bending of signals. Various factors, such as temperature, pressure, humidity, and satellite elevation, contribute for the bending of the signal [33]. The tropospheric effect, like atmospheric refraction, is influenced by satellite elevation and becomes more pronounced with increasing height. Modeling the troposphere helps reduce positional bias in GNSS data processing, enhancing its effectiveness. The tropospheric delay is caused by pressure, humidity, and temperature, which are responsible for most signal delays for GNSS accuracy applications[13].

2.7.6 Multipath Errors

While traveling to the earth's surface, GNSS signals interact with different surfaces, such as buildings, trees, forests, canyons, and other adjacent elevation structures. The signal interference is created from reflected waves, leading to a bidirectional path that causes signal distortion. The GNSS signal from the space is reflected in one or many ways before reaching the receiver's antenna. Thus, an elongation of the duration of time causes multiple errors that cause subsequent delays before the signal reaches the receiver, resulting in a specific amount of distance inaccuracy depending upon the duration of time, which is the wavelength reaching the receiver antenna [34]. The prolongation of error is generally based on the surface or medium where a signal encounter, generally medium-like water bodies, urban canyons, and vegetation medium where reflection of wave signal takes longer to reach the receiver [35].

2.7.7 Synchronization Error

A timing discrepancy between satellites and receivers and signal transmission and reception variations lead to delays, known as propagation errors. These delays often result from atmospheric conditions or multipath interference. The diffraction can cause signal elongation to worsen timing accuracy in synchronization. These errors can originate from both the satellite and the receiver. The satellite's location, orbital position, and clock synchronization errors can cause precise positioning to differ during mapping. Similarly, the device cannot work fully efficiently when the receiver has unusual hardware components, deficient internal parts, and a mislocated antenna setup with false calibration. In general, all factors create delays in communication and signal processing from satellite to receiver. Here, the size of the antenna and its orientation play significant roles in error management and in achieving centimeter-level accuracy [25].

2.8. Receiver-related errors

The errors are related to the receiver's hardware component settings and geographical location, which can hinder ability of receiver GNSS signals. Several factors can contribute

to mediocre performance and reduced receiver sensitivity. These include poorly designed and improperly calibrated hardware and incorrect placement of the receiver device in its geographical location.

2.8.1 Receiver noise

Those error noises are generated during analogue to digital conversion, where tracking loops, including Phase-Locked Loops (PLL) for carrier phases and Delay-Locked Loops (DLL) for code tracking, maintain synchronization with the satellite signals in the correlation process and band-widths measurement process by receivers. When they are uncorrelated then it is hard to model, and about 1 % of the wavelength signal is in carrier phase measurement, potentially leading to inaccuracies at the millimeter level. For instance, for the GPS L1 signal, where the wavelength is 19 cm, the error corresponds to approximately 1.9 mm.

a) Receiver antenna positioning errors.

Those errors are associated with inaccuracies in the positioning of the receiver antenna due to misalignment, positioning, or design failure of the GNSS electronic processing, which affects the quality of the signals and displays misleading results in calculations. The wrongly designed antenna has undermined the signal-receiving quality and low performances, whereas mispositioned antennae are inefficient in signal tracking and higher multipath signals. These factors can potentially lead to signal errors during the acquisition process. In real-time, signals are not always precise due to factors like multipath errors, signal breaking, reduced power levels, signals from different satellites, signals affected by the satellite's motion, receiver's displacement, different time shifts, and propagation delay from the satellite to the receiver.

2.9. Mitigation Techniques

A fixed GNSS antenna receives continuous satellite signals, ensuring minimal errors and high positional accuracy. Optimal performance occurs in open areas with few obstructions. Precision survey-grade antennas with choke rings minimize ground reflection interference in static positioning, whereas, for kinematic positioning, the antenna is mounted on a moving platform designed to receive signals in motion continuously. Positioning the antenna is challenging due to potential signal interference [14].

2.9.1 Augmentation System

The augmentation system means boosting performance; it is conducted by adding technical infrastructure designed to support the improvement of satellite navigation associated with other attributes like precision, reliability, and accuracy. The augmentation process primarily works by combining other technologies and exchanging data with other techniques that are applied to improve the system's accuracy. Applying that assessment in the GNSS for preciseness and accuracy for positioning and timing for improvement during the survey application. These augmentation methods are currently in practice, like fault detection, where wrong signal reaching analysis before reaching the receiver, and pseudo-range residual monitoring, where a discrepancy between the apparent distance measured from a satellite and the expected range determined by the receiver's clock and the satellite's position. The main types of augmentation systems that are currently in use are the Satellite Augmentation System (SBAS) and the Ground-Based Augmentation System (GBAS) [34]. These systems work together to enhance accuracy and reliability in satellite navigation applications.

a) Satellite-Based Augmentation (SBAS)

The SBAS augmentation techniques are designed to enhance the GNSS signal accuracy, dependability, and consistency by broadcasting corrected data from the several ground stations located near the survey points. When surveying, the survey stations receive and measure signals from satellites as well as additional noises from surroundings, this mixture of signal influences the received signal. SBAS provides services for correcting or modifying

signal measurements during navigation by giving information about the integrity of these same signals, allowing the re-transmitting of the data in the central constellations and identical format across a wide area on the geostationary satellite [36]. Since geo-satellites are situated on the earth's surface, they seek to enhance the accuracy and dependability of GNSS information [37, 38].

i) Few examples of Augmentation System for SBAS

The Space-Based Augmentation System (SBAS) includes various systems such as the American Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS), the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS), the Russian System (SBCM), the Japanese System (MSAS), and the Indian System (GAGAN). WAAS, operated by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), provides precise navigation technology [39], covering a large area and offering significant benefits. Additionally, the correction of the broadcast frequency is carried out with the help of geostationary satellites with an additional GNSS receiver for correction.

b) Ground-Based Augmentation (GBAS)

It was created to serve and support precise survey operation using terrestrial radio signals or network data, where transmission of data takes place between user and surveying ground stations also known as reference center. Based on varying locations, radio transmitters transmit information to the user based, local and regional coverage in real-time corrections. The local supporting receivers are actively working on an augmentation system with a certain range of kilometers distance using ultra-high frequency for communication.

Few examples of the Ground Regional Augmentation System (GRAS) that support larger area coverage are the Local Area Augmentation System (LAAS) and Differential GPS(DGPS), which provide coverage by transmitting corrections signals from ground-based stations for improving accuracy, especially in those areas of poor satellite visibility.

2.9.2 Static -Kinematic Positioning (Antenna Prospective)

GNSS receiver antennas are used in various positioning modes for signal reception, which can be either stationary or mobile. Depending on their positions, the antennas provide different measurement ranges for satellite signals based on the operating mode. In static positioning, the antenna is fixed and immovable. A fixed GNSS antenna receives continuous satellite signals, ensuring minimal errors and high positional accuracy. Optimal performance occurs in open areas with few obstructions. Precision survey-grade antennas with choke rings minimize ground reflection interference in static positioning, whereas, for kinematic positioning, the antenna is mounted on a moving platform designed to receive signals in motion continuously. Positioning the antenna is challenging due to potential signal interference [14].

2.10. Carrier-Based Relative Technique

Two primary measurement techniques are utilized for carrier phase measurements which are single differences and double differences. These approaches might effectively address GNSS signaling errors like satellite or receiver clock bias error. Various strategic time differential methods are implemented while the satellite is in motion, incorporating both receiver and satellite differentials. For the centimeter-level accuracy achievement, the frequently differential method is applied to mitigate the impact of ionospheric propagation errors, However, dual frequency GNSS or ionospheric models are used to reduce ionospheric propagation errors. Secondly, double difference techniques can simultaneously compare signals from receivers and satellites for further correction. Using this approach, clock biases can be effectively eliminated from both receivers and satellites [25].

a) Single Differences

A single-differential technique is employed with two receivers to measure signals from a single satellite for higher accuracy. Using this technique, some errors can be eliminated.

GNSS measurements, two separate receivers are used, with one receiver serving as the known reference position with the known location. The measurement is conducted using single differential techniques. By calculating the differences, the clock bias (pseudo distance) from a single satellite can be eliminated. It has been observed that atmospheric biases and orbital errors generated by both receivers are similar.

b) Double difference

The double difference refers to the disparity's measurement between two satellites and two receivers, which eliminates clock bias in receivers and satellites. This can be achieved by first comparing the differences at a specific time for the same satellite and comparing those differences between two satellites. The double difference combines disparities between two receivers and two satellites that cancel the clock biases from both, resulting in improved positional accuracy.

c) Base station

This method uses two receivers: a base station located at a known reference point and a rover at an unknown location. The base station continuously gathers data, allowing for single differential techniques. Compared to the distance to the satellite, the relatively short distance between the base station and the rover helps to eliminate clock bias (pseudo-range) errors. Because both receivers experience similar atmospheric and orbital errors, this approach significantly improves measurement accuracy [40].

a) DGNSS Methods

DGNSS refers to Differential GNSS, a method applied to correct or rectify inaccuracies and improve accuracy in high-precision scenarios. It involves a base station, a moveable rover, or a receiver equipped with a GNSS receiver and linked with the communication channel for

synchronization. The coordinates of the position of the base station, where the base receiver is placed at the known location, using this correction technique, the satellite data received in the base station continuously compares real-time data on a known area with the GNSS calculated position, the difference between their values. By transmitting those corrections to the rover in real-time. The rover's positioning errors are adjusted from the base station, ensuring precise location and reliable data, especially in the forest setting [14, 41].

b) Real-Time Kinematics (RTK)

This is one of the best techniques for correcting GNSS receiver data. This approach is used as fix or moving mode as kinematic mode, where carrier phase measurement techniques are used for real-time or post-processing correction, which are applied and employed to achieve accurate measurements. This method involves utilizing one base station along with one or more moving receivers or rovers, to rebroadcast the phase measurement obtained from the base station [42]. It has been observed that the highest level of accuracy can be achieved when there is availability of 5-6 satellites, especially in the forest region where multipath and signal noises are prevalent. In such practice, the stationary receiver rebroadcasts the phase of the carrier signal that has been measured, and the mobile units compare their phase movement with that of the receiver at the base station. This allows for the generation of double differences, which helps resolve carrier-phase ambiguities, significantly reducing but not eliminating other positioning errors. The resulting relative positions are accurate to the millimeter scale and then converted into an absolute position by referencing it to the position of the base receiver. However, it is essential to notice that the precision of the roving receiver's specific location is limited to the same level as that of the base receiver [13, 43].

Figure 11: RTK positioning techniques with rover antenna [13]

CHAPTER 6

2.11. GNSS other satellite constellations

2.11.1 GLONASS

a) Space Segment

The space segment of GLONASS consists of twenty-four satellites, with twenty-one operational and three spares, spread across three orbital planes. It operates using two principles: Standard Precision Services (SPS), which can be used for civilians for medium positioning accuracy, as well as High Precision Service (HPS), a service that offers higher enhancements for authorized users that consists of governmental as well as military agencies. The satellites transmit signals in L1 at 1602 MHz and L2 at 1246 MHz. The GLONASS satellites are positioned at an inclination angle of 64.8° on a circular orbit at 19,100 km, revolving on 11 hr 15 min 44 sec at 120° with longitude. It includes twenty-four satellites, of which twenty-one are operational, and three are spares, arranged across three orbital planes.

Figure 12: GLONASS Satellite Constellation 2017 [21]

b) Control Segment

The ground control segment measures and predicts the positions of individual satellites using ephemeris data. It uploads predicted ephemeris, clock corrections, and almanac information into the navigation message. It also synchronizes time with a satellite clock using GLONASS.UTC (SU), also known as Universal Time Coordinated of Russia UTC(SU). Additionally, it controls spacecraft, routinely keeps maintenance and management tasks, and tracks the satellites [16].

2.11.2 Galileo

a) Space Segment

Galileo's space segment consists of thirty operating satellites, with three spares and twenty-seven functional satellites. They are positioned on three orbital planes on the equatorial plane of 56° (longitudinal angle of 120°). The space segments comprising six satellites were followed by four In-Orbit Validation (IOV) satellites and two operation satellites with Full Operational Capability (FOC). The primary purpose is to provide open service (OS) for public access, High Accuracy Service for selective users for a higher level of precision, and Public Regulated Service (PRS) for the users for secure and reliable navigation, especially safety of life under operation [30].

It consists of an orbit that is supported by a ground segment and focuses for providing help and assistance rather than signals on the operating (E1, E5a, and E5b) are single and dual compatible frequencies related with L1 and L5 band GPS, i.e. Different frequencies Galileo operates on the range 1176-1207 MHz near GPS L1 and 1575.42 MHz of the GPS L5 frequency [28, 44].

Figure 13: Galileo Satellite a) GSAT010x b)GSAT02xx [21]

b) Control Segment

The main function of the Galileo control segment is to assist, command, and control periodic interactions with other satellites and their corresponding stations, sharing the operational data for synchronization to the ground control points and monitoring them. Since it is designed to be interoperable and compatible with multi-constellation satellite systems, it also includes uploading GPS data and deploying messages to Galileo satellites. It also performs other tasks like multi-purpose operations of satellites, such as flight dynamics, operation preparation, training, and validation activities, as well as monitoring and controlling. [16]. Apart from that, these operations rely on the orbital status of the satellite.

2.11.3 Compass /Bei-Dou

A navigation system from China consisting of five geostationary satellites and thirty non-geostationary satellites. The second-generation navigation system has two different orbits with a fifty-five ° inclination for navigation. It lies on the medium orbit at 21,500 km and uses three channels with three different frequencies: B1 using 1559.052 to 1591.788 MHz, B2 using 1166.22 to 1217.37 MHz, and B3 1250.618 to 1286.423 MHz. It provides the

service on a global scale with an accuracy of 10, a timing accuracy of 20 nanoseconds, and a velocity accuracy of 0.2 m/s [38].

2.12. Quasi-Zenith Satellite System (QZSS)

The Quasi -zenith Satellite System (QZSS) is a regional navigation satellite system developed by Japan , consisting of four satellite positioned in inclined geosynchronous orbits at approximate 39, 911 km with an inclination of 39° to 47° [38].QZSS become operational in 2013 with three satellite and achieved full operational capability in 2018 with four satellites. The regional GNSS constellation having three operating frequencies similar to GPS i.e. 1575.42 MHz, 1176.45 MHz and 1278.75 MHz and aiming to provide broad range of positioning capabilities , especially in the urban sector environment and media applications [16].

Comprehensive overview of the significant local and worldwide satellite navigation systems, where (NaVIC) represents, Navigation with Indian Constellations, (GSO) represents Geostationary orbit, (IGSO) Inclined Geostationary Orbit.

System	GPS	GLONASS	BeiDou	Galileo	NavIC	QZSS
Owner	United States	Russia	China	European Union	India	Japan
Orbital altitude	20,188	19,130	21,150	23,222	36,000	36,000
Total Number of Orbit	1	1	1	1	2	1
Orbital Planes	6	3	3	3	2	4

Total planes in constellation	6 MEO	3 MEO	3 GEO, 3 IGSO, 3 MEO	3 MEO	3 GEO 4 IGSO	3 GSO, 1 GEO
Total number of operational satellites	31	24	35	22	08	04
Period	11.97 h	11.26 h	12.63 h	14.00 h	23.93 h	23.93 h
Number of satellites	72	24 in 3 orbital planes with ascending nodes are 120°	5 GEO, 30 MEO	30	14 (8 active, 1 failed, 5 planned)	7 (4 satellites in a constellation and 3 satellites are planned for 2030)
Latest Status	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational
Year of first launch	1978	1982	2000	2011	2013	2010
Fully Operational	Fully Operational	Fully operational	Fully operational	Fully operational	NA	Fully operational
Horizontal Accuracy	500-30 cm	5-10m (with vertical accuracy)	3.46m public, 2.6m. Asia Pacific, 10 cm encrypted	1 m (public), 1 cm(encrypted)	1 m (public), 10 cm (encrypted)	PNT<10m
Reference Coordinate System	WGS84	PE-90	CGCS2000	GTRF	ITRF	WGS84 (Augmented)

Table 1: GNSS global and regional system overview [38]

3. Methodology

3.1. Current state of GNSS positioning /locating in forests

This section describes the approach used to find literature search on the GNSS positioning in the forest. The numerous questionnaires were formulated for searching for information from various peer-reviewed articles based on field surveys, especially GPS/GNSS navigation on forest.

3.2. Questionnaire for the literature findings

- i) What problems does the paper address when applying GNSS in forestry settings? Why is it a problem?
- ii) Why is GNSS not working in these settings? What are the addressed shortcomings?
- iii) What are the main suspected errors introduced by GNSS in their settings?
- iv) How do they (try to) solve the problem?
- v) What accuracy do they report? Did it improve?
- vi) How did they establish their results?
- vii) Which (Suspected) errors of GNSS did they (probably improve)

Questionnaire after literature findings

- i) What challenges are GNSS facing when locating and positioning in a forest environment?
- ii) What sort of positional accuracy and precision have been achieved?
- iii) Proposed methods and approaches (what are proposed solutions)

iv) Approach for obtaining results.

Findings of the literature on the **current state of the art** where GNSS showing problems in forests,

3.2.1 Issues of GNSS in forestry regions

a) A detailed examination of the literature on GNSS-based positioning in forested regions.

During the literature research on GNSS locating and positioning in the forest, on the current state of the art, multiple studies were carried out that focused on the GNSS location in the forest. Based on the previous studies and scientific findings from various navigational research studies conducted on the scientific platform, on different techniques on accuracy and positioning using GPS, earlier findings have been documented on global web resources [45], in various scientific forms like articles, journals, manuscripts, conference papers, and many more that briefly describe earlier experimental research, positioning, and navigation. For all positioning and navigations, a significant amount of research has been focused on positioning in forests [46], the technology used in positioning, the challenges it faced, factors contributing to difficulties in locating, and potential solutions for addressing positional accuracies to obtain ranging from meters to centimeters scale.

b) Common challenges for locating /positioning in forests

GNSS principles are based on the positioning, navigation, and location of objects between satellites and receivers [47]. The positioning of GNSS signals is of great concern to surveyors and researchers. The satellite waves travel from a long way to reach the receiver in the forest [48]. Forests are a prime example of GNSS signal interaction and the most complicated area for signalling [49]. When the signal reaches the forest, it interacts with the vast forest canopy and vegetation [10]. The signals interact with forest environmental agents like wind,

moisture, humidity, and other tree attributes like leaves, stems, and branches, collectively called foliage. As a forest consists of various vegetation, long trees compact with a basal stand with an extended canopy. The compact canopy prevents the signal from reaching the receiver antenna quickly. The resulting wave signal tries to enter from those sources but gets obscured, blocked, discounted, or reflected [50]. This causes the signal to get more propagations and develop multiple directions due to the wave's deviation [51].

c) Agents for wave propagation cause issues that prevent GNSS from working accurately in forested areas

Several studies and literature sources claim that GNSS wave signals struggle to reach the close canopy and in the forest during positioning [52]. The forest acts as a barrier in a close position rather than in the open sky. The forest and its topography, dense canopy, complexity of forest environment, geography and pattern of formation, location as well as steepness, weather phenomena, clouds, inclination or the steepness are obstructions that are regularly observing agents in a forest stand that lead to signaling issues [53]. Those issues are directly connected with the device or antenna. The accuracy of GNSS in a forested environment is affected by the device parameters, which include processing mode and observation conditions. The unique conditional features of each forest site determine the extent of these effects. Factors such as multipath effects and signal losses due to the forest canopy can reduce accuracy by blocking and reflecting signals. For the underlying problem, specific studies are necessary to assess the performance of a device and processing mode that is accurate under varying canopy conditions, as achieving predicted accuracy under ideal conditions in forest environments is practically challenging [54].

d) A common agent that causes GNSS problems in forestry

The term "canopy" refers to the upper layer of a tree, consisting of branches and leaves that form a dense covering in the highest layer of a forest, significantly impacting the ecosystem

[55]. The canopy regulates the understory's sunlight, temperature, and moisture levels in the forest. In the context of GNSS, a canopy refers to any physical barrier created by dense tree cover that obstructs satellite signals from reaching GNSS to the receiver(s). The thick foliage of trees can absorb, reflect, or refract GNSS signals, leading to signal attenuation, multipath errors, or complete signal blockage, resulting in positioning errors during navigation or mapping for the GNSS receiver [56]. Additionally, leaf covering on their distribution area is another crucial component in positional accuracy, as higher leaves areas consist of a greater volume of leaves and moisture. The moisture and leaves indirectly affect signal quality and accuracy determination [57].

As vegetation and trees can obstruct satellite signals, reducing signal intensity, this phenomenon is known as signal blockage, creating interference and weakening signals [49, 58].

3.2.2 Primary sources of errors regarding positional accuracy in the forest

a) Signal attenuation on forest location.

The signal coming from the satellite during the arrival gets attenuated, weakened, distorted, discontinued, or reflected away from objects [10, 57]. As the signal bounces, it backs off from multiple components of trees, like leaves, branches, and stems. Those retrieved signal loses their original intensity, finally reducing the signal strength when traveling through the medium or encountering obstacles [10]. It can also be understood as a process of weakening of the signal strength during traveling through multiple mediums, when encountering forest dynamics like wind, weather, and retracting paths and refracted as well as diffracted, resulting in an impact on the accuracy and as well as positioning [8, 45].

b) Multipath in the forest

Multipath refers to the phenomenon where signals travel along multiple pathways due to reflective surfaces from the environment. As satellite signals travel from space, they gradually lose strength, with some portions absorbed by atmospheric particles- a process

described by the Beer Lamber law [10]. This absorption, along with environmental interferences, causes signals to deviate from the original trajectory, often splitting into multiple directions due to reflective surfaces encountered along the way [57, 59] before reaching the receiver's antenna, the signal reflects off from various surfaces, such as forests and their components like leaves, branches, water bodies, mountains, human-made infrastructures and ground, causing delays and distortions that take longer time and distance to reach the receiver, subsequently bringing erroneous point location [10], as signal lowering their original quality [8]. When the signal bounces back from the object at various times, the bounced signal cannot detect the correct position on the preferred object. Due to those effects, GNSS faced challenges from multiple agents, it does not work as effectively as desired in forest settings due to the multipath effect [60].

c) Satellite visibility and geometry

For better accurate positioning from GNSS, satellite geometry and its availability play a crucial role [10]. The higher the number of satellite signals reachable inside the canopy, the better and more optimal the positioning would be, even in the presence of more vegetation and in higher environmental interferences. Signal interferences on forests mostly relies on canopy and their gaps [49]. The wider the opening gap of canopies allows more signals to enter into the desired location, whereas less opened or partially opened canopies do not letting direct signals to reach the receiver antenna, creating obstacles in positioning [50]. The satellite visibility and geometry also change as forests and their vegetation change with the seasons, and as canopy cover changes, gaps and openings also vary, which always fluctuates in positional accuracy.

4. RESULT

This section addresses the current practices and recent trends that were found in the state of the art when GNSS was introduced in the forest setting.

4.1. Positioning pattern heterogeneous landscape on forest

For accurate positioning and navigation, land topography plays a crucial role, as earth surfaces consist of various forms of land shapes and land covers that consist of different types of forests. The selected journal articles are examples of GNSS positioning in the forests that were found in various geographical locations on the entire globe, from the Valsain forest of the mountainous region of Spain [11], Wakayama forest area of Japan [61], European Beech Forest [62], Coniferous forest of Poland [10], different types of forest regions of the U.S.A, including the mature deciduous forest of Athens to Georgia, the Coastal mountain region forest of Oregon and the Douglas temperate rainforest of Washington [49, 60, 63], Whitehall Forest, Georgia Athens [64], European Scots Pine Forest Northern Sweden [65], Olsztyn Forest Poland [66] to Larix pine tree forest Davutpasa region in India [67], in which GNSS positioning and accuracy measurement were carried out.

4.2. Associate factors affecting GNSS positioning and accuracy in diverse types of forests and landscapes based on resources.

Prior research has examined the application of GNSS for achieving precise positioning to attain the highest level of accuracy. Those studies have delved into the most suitable hardware for accurate positioning [68], determining the critical parameters for achieving precision and exploring other potential solutions [56]. The research has delved into existing navigation and positioning methodologies, measurement configurations, strategies for attaining accuracy at different scales, and the environmental factors that impact accuracy, such as wind, humidity, seasons, and the geography of the forest stand. In the field experiment described in the literature, multiple technological improvements and practices were carried out while addressing positioning errors regarding GPS or GNSS in the forest. Considering the transformative nature of forests [8], where one technique is not

suitable, alternate and unique techniques have to be applied in the forest for the best suitable measurement. During the calculation, numerous types of mapping receivers have been utilized from private as well as research organizational sectors for consumer-level [68], allowing different accuracy in different forest zones like temperate, tropical, Mediterranean, and polar areas, where those methods were already tested to evaluate GNSS in forest environments [69], like autonomous GPS with post-processing, differential GPS (DGPS), RTK, and (PPP) [54].

The methodology is adopted for accuracy calculation.

a) Positioning accuracy

The terms accuracy and precision are commonly used term for measuring object positioning and calculation from GNSS signal to the receiver; both terms are used for an object located on the earth's space for nearness, where measurements are primarily carried out for GPS or GNSS measurement and are calculated based on precision and accuracy [61]. Accuracy is defined as any sample mean's proximity to its true value, whereas precision is defined as the proximity of the recurrent or repeated observation; when an object moves from its original position, then errors are produced. In GPS surveying, stationary objects can result in errors due to wrong signals during navigation. For the understanding accuracy, errors are further divided into horizontal positioning or horizontal errors that represent the east-west axis or x-y co-ordinate and vertical positioning, the north-south axis that is carried out for the vertical positioning, i.e. height and elevation measurement of z co-ordinate [11].

Here, σ_x , and σ_y , representing standard deviation along x and y axes obtaining the standard error of positioning directions. Similarly $\sigma_{H-accuracy}$, and $\sigma_{H-precision}$ representing horizontal accuracy and horizontal precision, which representing the positional standard errors on the x- axes (σ_x) and y-axis(σ_y), respectively. The symbols, $-x_{true}$ and $-y_{true}$ are the true positions with x and y axes that are supplying parameters for evaluating horizontal accuracy .

$$\sigma_{H-precision} = \sqrt{(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2)}$$

Horizontal accuracy is given by $\sigma_{H-accuracy}$,

$$\sigma_{H-accuracy} = \sqrt{((\bar{x} - x_{true})^2 + (\bar{y} - y_{true})^2)} \quad [61]$$

One more accuracy is called positional accuracy, which is defined as the horizontal distance between the GPS's valid reference point and the acquired positions [70].

b) Measurement- mode used during satellite signal acquisition.

Float mode is based upon the actual value of sequences for the carrier phase between sequences receiver and satellite. It is the close approximate value and is likely to change with real-value [62].

Fix mode is a stable or locked mode where the GNSS receiver provides real values after solving integer ambiguities from carrier phase measurement [62].

Static measurement keeps the GNSS receiver stationary to collect the data quickly and helps decrease the positional error. However, in continuous measurement, data are obtained smoothly in constant motion, and they are simultaneously collected on a real-time scale, mainly used on application techniques like DGPS and (RTK) [71].

4.3. Essential information of twenty-five articles focusing on GNSS located on forest.

Article [I]

According to the author [72], “Assessing Horizontal Accuracy of Inventory Plots in Forests with Different Mixes of Tree Species Composition and Development Stage” (Viglas, Slovakia, 2018).

This study aimed to evaluate the horizontal accuracy of GNSS receivers in various forest types, including broadleaf forests and old canopies. By utilizing Topcon Hiper GGD and Topcon FC-25A receivers, the researchers reported a horizontal accuracy of 14.6 m under the canopy and 11.44 m outside the canopy. The findings emphasize the importance of

employing DGPS and mapping-grade GPS receivers to enhance positional accuracy in complex forest environments.

Article [II]

As outlined in the article [11], “Accuracy and Precision of GPS Receivers Under Forest Canopies in a Mountainous Environment” (Valsain Forest, Spain, 2008).

This study focused on assessing GNSS signal interruption and accuracy within mountainous, forested regions and utilized several GNSS receivers, including Leica GS50, SR530, Topcon Hiper Pro, and GMS2. The results indicated that the horizontal RMSE accuracy error was 1.78 m under forest canopies, whereas it was 1.68 m on a plane. The article suggests that improved performance can be attained through dual-frequency receivers in the forest for more accuracy rather than handheld receivers, recommends extended observation times, and recommends at least 15 minutes of observation time for optimal precision.

Article [III]

As indicated in the article [61], “Comparing the Precision and Accuracy of GPS Positioning in Forested Areas” (Wakayama, Japan, 2000).

This research involved the use of a Trimble 4600 LS GNSS base station and Trimble Pathfinder Pro-XR receivers in a forested area to analyze GPS accuracy. Data collection occurred over 20 minutes at four different locations, revealing that the horizontal accuracy from autonomous GPS ranged from 2.42 m to 6.67 m, while differential corrected GPS achieved a remarkable range of 0.09 m to 0.44 m. The study advocates the use of DGPS in areas with thinner canopies to improve measurement processes and overall accuracy.

Article [IV]

The author asserts that [10], “Impact of Forest Spatial Structure on the Variation of the Multipath Phenomenon of Navigation Satellite Signals “ (Poland, 2015-2016).

Investigating the influence of forest spatial structure on GNSS signal multipath phenomena, this study employed Trimble R8 GNSS, Stonex S9, Topcon Hiper Pro, and Leica Viva GS08 Plus receivers. Conducted over two years with each survey lasting 25 minutes, the results showed a significant reduction in multipath effects in open spaces compared to forest zones. The study recommends increasing antenna height and observation time while selecting appropriate GNSS equipment to optimize positional accuracy.

Article [V]

As outlined by author [49], “Impact of Forest Canopy on Quality and Accuracy of GPS Measurements” (Indiana, USA, 1999).

This research assessed how seasonal changes in forest canopy density affected GPS measurement accuracy within a mixed-hardwood forest. Utilizing AshTech Surveying Grade GPS and Trimble Pro-XL receivers, multiple sessions were conducted over 3-hour intervals in both leaf-on and leaf-off conditions. The findings indicated that leaf-off conditions significantly enhanced positional accuracy, suggesting that averaging positional fixes can further improve GPS performance and that upgrading receiver quality is beneficial for managing signal interference.

Article [VI]

As noted in text [62], “The Effect of Mounting Height on GNSS Receiver Accuracy in Forest Conditions” (Gluchow, Poland, 2014). Evaluating how antenna height influences GNSS receiver accuracy, this study utilized a Geodetic dual-frequency Topcon Hiper Pro receiver. The results highlighted that the best positional accuracy of 0.54 m was achieved at a 10 m antenna height during leafless conditions. The research concludes that employing DGNSS techniques along with increased antenna height significantly improves accuracy in forested environments.

Article [VII]

According to the author [60], “Tree Location Measurement Accuracy with a Mapping-Grade GPS Receiver Under Forest Canopy” (United States, 2010).

This study focused on the accuracy of GPS measurements under forest canopies, using Trimble GeoXH and Trimble ProXH receivers while implementing an offset method to minimize interference from tree stems. The researchers collected a minimum of thirty data points for each tree's position. Results indicated that differential correction provided superior accuracy compared to autonomous GPS, leading to the recommendation of differential correction methods for enhanced precision measurement in forested areas.

Article [VIII]

As highlighted from the authors [73], “Rapid Static Positioning Using a Four-System GNSS Receiver in the Forest Environment” (Rogow, Poland).

This study used Geodetic Stonex S900A and GIS Class Receiver CHC LT700H to evaluate the accuracy and precision of commercial GNSS receivers in heterogeneous forest environments. Findings revealed that the Stonex S900A achieved an accuracy of 0.91 m, while the LT700H receiver provided 1.29 m accuracy. The article suggests employing differential correction and combining satellite constellations to improve overall accuracy and reduce positional errors in forest settings.

Article [IX]

Based on the evidenced mentioned on article [63], “Multipath Mitigation Under Forest Canopies: A Choke Ring Antenna Solution” (Georgia, USA, 2008).

This research investigated the effectiveness of choke ring antennas versus beacon antennas in reducing GNSS signal multipath errors under forest canopies. Using Trimble ProXR receivers, the study reported horizontal accuracy ranging from 0.35 m to 0.69 m during leaf-off conditions, while applying DGPS correction from the beacon antenna showed positional

accuracy ranging from 4.9 m to 6.1 m during leaf-on seasons. The study advocates choke ring antennas and post-processed DGPS to enhance accuracy.

Article [X]

Insight from the article [74], “Effects of Canopy and Multi-Epoch Observation on Single Point Positioning Errors of a GNSS in Coniferous and Broadleaved Forests” (China, 2019).

Focusing on the accuracy of GNSS positioning in mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, this study employed a minimum observation time of 10 minutes per tree with data recorded every second. Utilizing a Galaxy 6 RTK GNSS along with a total station, the results indicate that accuracy varied significantly between trees species, recording 12.13 m for coniferous forests and 15.11 m for broadleaf forests. The article emphasizes the importance of differential correction techniques to mitigate positioning errors.

Article [XI]

As referred on the article [75], “Horizontal Accuracy and Applicability of Smartphone GNSS Positioning in Forests (Slovakia, 2014-2015).

This study aimed to assess the real-time horizontal accuracy of smartphone GNSS receivers in various forest conditions. Employing a Total Station Theodolite and Trimble Nomand, the research found that positional accuracy ranged from 4.96 m to 11.45 m during leaf-on conditions. In comparison, it varied between 4.51 m to 6.72 m during leaf-off conditions. The results indicated that average positional fixes and high-sensitivity GNSS receivers are essential for improving accuracy in challenging environments.

Article [XII]

According to the authors [70], “Point Accuracy of Combined Pseudo-Range and Carrier Phase Differential GPS Under Forest Canopy” (Norway, 1999).

This research focused on the accuracy of combined pseudo-range and carrier phase differential GPS in forest environments. Trimble Geo Explorer and Ashtech Super C/A receivers were used. The study showed that C/A code accuracy ranged from 1.17 m to 3.70 m, while carrier phase accuracy was 0.79 m to 2.25 m. The article suggests using advanced hardware in varied environments and emphasizes the need for differential GPS techniques to improve accuracy.

Article [XIII]

As outlined in the article [51], “Analysis of GNSS Receiver Accuracy in the Forest Environment” (Gluchow Forest, Poland, 2009)

This study investigated GNSS receiver accuracy using RTK techniques in fixed and float measurement modes. Employing dual-frequency Topcon HiperPro and Top Surv FC-200 with an 18 m aluminum pole, the research reported mean positional accuracy of 0.20 m for fixed stations and 0.67 m for float measurements, with overall precision around ± 0.03 m. The study recommends the use of fixed station solutions for improved accuracy in forest environments.

Article [XIV]

From the article [67], “Low-Cost GNSS Receiver RTK Performance in Forest Environments (India, 2020).

Aiming to explore the impact of various GNSS combinations on RTK systems for precision and reliability, this research utilized Leica GR50 and AR25 antennas, along with PPP from AUSPOS. The findings indicated that low-cost rovers could achieve meter-level horizontal accuracy. The article concludes that extending observation time and utilizing high-quality GNSS receivers are crucial for improving accuracy in forest settings.

Article [XV]

As noted on the research paper [76], “Behavior of GPS Signal Interruption Probability Under Tree Canopies in Different Forest Conditions” (Kyoto, Japan, 2009-2010).

This study aimed to evaluate GPS signal interruption probabilities across various forest conditions, including coniferous, deciduous, and evergreen trees. The researchers utilized Leica GPS model SR530 as a rover, with Trimble GPS Total Station as the base. Results demonstrated that accuracy was better in open-sky conditions compared to dense canopies, and the study recommends longer observation periods (minimum 15 minutes) along with increasing antenna height to reduce interference from low-angle satellites.

Article [XVI]

The paper emphasizes on [77], “Seasonal Variation of GPS Accuracy and Precision in Forest Road Mapping (Tehran, 2022).

This study explored the effects of seasonal variations on GPS accuracy and precision during forest road mapping. Employing Colorado 300 GNSS receivers, the results showed that accuracy in spring ranged from 24.45 m to 24.97 m, while other seasons exhibited accuracy between 56.10 m and 53.65 m. The article recommends employing positional averaging techniques and utilizing advanced smartphones to enhance accuracy during field operations.

Article [XVII]

From the authors [78] “Balancing Horizontal Accuracy and Data Collection Efficiency with Mapping-Grade GPS Receivers” (Northwest Corvallis, USA).

This research examined GPS accuracy in various forest zones utilizing mapping-grade GPS receivers such as Trimble GeoXH and GeoXT. Conducted in controlled environments, the study found that post-processed kinematics achieved open-sky accuracy between 1-2 cm, whereas accuracy declined to between 1-10 meters inside the canopy. The article recommends implementing differential GPS and post-processed kinematics to improve overall accuracy.

Article [XVIII]

According to the author [1], “Evaluating Global Positioning System Accuracy for Forest Biomass Transportation Tracking Within Varying Forest Canopy (USA, 2009).

This study focused on tracking vehicles for biomass transportation in a forest canopy that transitioned from young to mature trees. Using three sets of Visiontec VGPS 900 receivers, the findings indicated that accuracy varied between 5.9 m and 14.3 m in mature forest areas. The article emphasizes consistency and reliability in data operation receivers and consumer-grade GPS receivers to improve overall accuracy in challenging forest conditions.

Article [XIX]

As listed on the article [56], “Performance of GPS Precise Point Positioning Under Conifer Forest Canopies” (Norway, July-August 2005).

This research evaluated GPS Precise Point Positioning (PPP) under coniferous forest canopies, utilizing a Javad Legacy 20 dual-frequency receiver for both pseudo-range and carrier phase observations. The study reported that mean accuracy ranged from 0.27 m to 0.88 m over a two-hour observation period, though it declined to between 0.95 m and 3.48 m during a 15-minute observation. The authors recommend that longer observation times enhance accuracy compared to DGPS.

Article [XX]

As outlined in the article [9], “Effect of Occupation Time on the Horizontal Accuracy of a Mapping-Grade GNSS Receiver Under Dense Forest Canopy” (Washington West, 2013). This study assessed how various occupation times impacted the horizontal accuracy of a GNSS receiver in dense forest conditions. Utilizing Trimble GeoXH6000 and Javad Triumph 1 receivers, the results indicated an accuracy of 1.85 m. The article recommends using differential post-processing techniques and survey-grade receivers, particularly with extended occupation times, to achieve better accuracy in challenging forest environments.

Article [XXI]

According to the author [64], “ The Effects of Nearby Trees on the Positional Accuracy of GNSS Receivers in a Forest Environment” (Whitehall Forest, Georgia, 2023). This study evaluated the impact of nearby trees on GNSS receiver accuracy using a combination of devices, including a Garmin receiver, a Trimble receiver, and multiple smartphones. The findings indicated that horizontal accuracy ranged between 2 m and 5 m, depending on the specific receiver used. The article emphasizes that the proximity of trees significantly affects positional accuracy and advocates for the use of advanced GNSS receivers to improve measurement reliability.

Article [XXII]

As referred on article [65], “Reliable Technology of Centimeter GPS/GLONASS Surveying in Forest Environments”(Olsztyn, Poland, October 2012).

This research aimed at achieving centimeter-level accuracy in GPS/GLONASS surveying technology within forest environments. Using three Topcon Hiper Pro GNSS receivers, data collection lasted for 1.5 hours, revealing that the RTK horizontal method achieved an impressive accuracy of 3 cm, while the rapid static method reached 1.9 cm. The study recommends employing multiple receivers in a fixed geometric arrangement for optimal results.

Article [XXIII]

As mentioned on article [52] , “Assessment of the GNSS RTK For Application in Precision Forest Operation”(Geographical location and year -on Kangwon region of Korea in August 2022) on area of mixed forest where pinus tree species and coniferous forest were prevalent. According to the article, Evaluation of GNSS RTK positioning accuracy and range for precision forestry were done especially focusing on smart thinning and its impact on forest environmental factors. During the study period, the hardware setup used in the experiment equipment was Trimble R12i model were used one as rover and other as base station, some

additional hardware terrestrial Lidar sensor for controlling data and Vertex Laser Geo device for measuring trees.

For key accuracy, the GNSS -RTK showed an average horizontal RMSE of 0.26 m in larch stands and 0.48 m in Korean Pine stands, observed that higher density obstructed satellite signals and reduced accuracy. The article recommends improving GNSS RTK accuracy by placing equipment away from tree trunks to minimize signal obstructions and adjustment GNSS settings by adding external antennas in denser stands with high canopy and use of supplementary tools for tailoring high density forest enhancement of accuracy.

Article [XIV]

As outlined from text [79], “The Seasonal Effects of Deciduous Tree Foliage in CORS-GNSS Measurement” (Istanbul, Turkey, April-June 2012).

This study examined how seasonal variations in deciduous tree foliage influenced CORS-GNSS measurements. Utilizing Topcon Hiper Pro and Ashtech Z Max GPS receivers, the research indicated that vertical positioning accuracy ranged from ± 2 cm to ± 4 cm during leaf-off conditions but increased to ± 13 cm to ± 36 cm during leaf-on conditions. Horizontal accuracy varied between ± 1 cm to ± 3 cm when leaves were off and ± 1 cm to ± 8 cm when leaves were on. The article recommends using real-time correction data from reference stations and optimizing survey timing during leaf-off conditions.

Article [XXV]

The author reports on [80]” Horizontal Measurement Performance of Five Mapping-Grade GPS Receiver Configurations in Several Forested Settings” (Temperate Forest, 2006).

This research evaluated the horizontal measurement performance of five mapping-grade GPS receivers across different forested settings, explicitly focusing on the impact of dense canopies and complex terrain. The study utilized Trimble GeoXH GNSS receivers, and data collection was performed over various durations. The findings indicated that open-sky

accuracy was measured at 0.5 m after post-processing, young forest accuracy at 0.6 m, and closed canopy accuracy reached 1.7 m. The article strongly suggests using multiple combinations of GNSS constellations and high-sensitivity receivers for improved positioning technology.

4.4. Accuracy positioning in multiple contexts from various papers

Numerous studies have highlighted the accuracy associated with (GNSS) positioning in forested environments, revealing various precision levels and their associated experimental errors. Those findings indicate that positioning accuracy fluctuates across multiple contexts and settings, influenced by the distinct measurement techniques employed in forestry, which are also directly associated with environments. Similarly, alternative methodologies were utilized in the different forest zones used in the research. Each review addressed several topics, including enhancing accuracy through implementing hardware specifications, the techniques used to ensure reliability on the different geographical locations associated with seasons and time, and their implications for improving positional accuracy across various contexts and measurement models.

5. Result based on best accuracy.

5.1. GNSS positioning on forest – ranking horizontal accuracy.

The various accuracy from multiple articles presented on the current state of the art,

Serial number	Journal article number	Forest type	Horizontal Accuracy in m	Location
1	XXII	Normal	0.0188	Olsztyn, Poland, 2012
2	XXIV	Deciduous	0.05	Istanbul, Turkey, 2012
3	VIII	Mixed (Pinus& Larch)	0.74	Rogow, Poland, 2009

4	XXIII	Coniferous	0.26	Korea, 2022
5	XV	Coniferous	1.3	Kyoto, Japan, 2010
6	XIII	Broadleaved, Coniferous	0.073	Poland, 2009
7	V	Mixed hardwood	7.57	Indiana, USA, 1999
8	XX	Evergreen	0.97	Washington West 2013
9	XVII	Evergreen	2.64	Northwest Corvallis, USA, 2013
10	XIX	Coniferous	1.18	Norway, 2005
11	VI	Coniferous	0.01	Gluchow, Poland, 2014
12	XIV	Mixed	1.584	India, 2020
13	XI	Mixed Deciduous	4.51	Slovakia, 2014-2015
14	XII	Deciduous	2.7	Southeastern Norway, 1999
15	VII	Mixed deciduous	2.6	USA, Northwest Corvallis, 2010
16	II	Coniferous	3.164	Valsain Forest, Spain, 2008
17	III	Mixed	3.26	Wakayama, Japan, 2000
18	IX	Coniferous	3.45	Georgia, USA, 2008
19	XVIII	Coniferous, Broadleaf	11.49	USA, 2009
20	I	Coniferous	8.45	Viglas, Slovakia, 2018
21	X	Mixed	15.85	China, 2019
22	XXV	Temperate	1.1	Washington, USA, 2013
23	XV	Coniferous	1.3	Kyoto, Japan, 2010
24	XVI	Mixed	34.3263	Tehran, 2022
25	IV	Mixed	Not mentioned	Warsaw, Poland, 2015-2016

Table 2: RMSE error accuracy ranges from least error to most error horizontal positioning

Figure 14: RMSE accuracy on horizontal positioning from selected journals

5.2. Achieving cutting-edge accuracy through innovative model Augmentation techniques revealed in journal articles.

GPS and GNSS positioning accuracy in forest environments varies among GPS receivers. Several positioning techniques, single or combined, were used to improve accuracy in these areas. These techniques include RTK), Differential GPS (DGPS), precise point positioning (PPP), and various post-processing methods.

5.3. Groups of Articles - Based on applied correction techniques on different field surveys.

RTK Techniques - Article number (XXII, XIV, XXIV, X, XXIII)

Single Point Positioning -Article number (XXI, X)

DGPS – Article number (XVIII, XV, V, XVII, I, VI, IX, IV, VIII, II)

Hemispherical pictures recorded – Article number (XV, XXIII, V, IX)

Post-processing from ASG -EUPOS system: Article number (XXIII, XIII, VI)

5.4. Groups - analysis of GNSS signals on positioning systems operating under the challenging forest canopy.

Based on similar groups, the reviewed papers systematically categorize positioning accuracy records while performing GNSS positioning in a forest environment. The authors of articles (VIII, X, XIV, XXII, XXIII, and XIV, claim that with RTK and rapid static combination, a centimeter level of accuracy has been obtained during positioning.

a) RTK-based approaches: The review from [65], on the various studies demonstrate that RTK performance positioning on the numerous types of forest locations where the positioning accuracy Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was used, where survey was done on diverse forest locations. The best RMSE with 0.0188 m was observed on the coniferous forest of Olsztyn on Poland (article 22), on which rapid static and real kinematics were used. By using the application of CROS RTK, on the deciduous forest, field survey was conducted with accuracy (0.05) m in the month of June indicating well on the deciduous forest as compared to the evergreen forest. In contrast, other experiments conducted in Poland on mixed forests, i.e., coniferous and deciduous and forest-protected areas, in India, show 0.74 m and 1.584 m. It can be found that major differences in accuracy were observed because of forest structure. On the Pinus dominated forest [52] located on South Korea, where RMSE was measured was 0.26 m showing the moderate accuracy from pine needle canopy that degrading signal quality even RTK dual frequency receiver was used. Those studies show that RTK varying in various environmental factors and hardware settings as well as location.

b) GDPS/GNSS -applied on different environmental conditions –for horizontal accuracy

Article numbers (III, VII, XII, XX, XXV)

Reviews from various field surveys showing the effectiveness of the DGPS on the numerous forest zones showing the variation of RMSE values on various environmental settings. According to article 20, with the use of mapping grade dual frequency receiver the RMSE value was noted 0.97 m while surveying on the forest having the Douglas fir species on the mountainous region. On the temperate forest with the same species article 25, with differential correction of data from WAAS satellite system, RMSE value was 1.1 m, other study carried out on the similar location [60] showing higher positioning error with RMSE value of 2.64 m where forest consists of mixture of Douglas fir and broadleaves of Maple tree species where single frequency receiver was used as mapping device. On the hand, navigation survey conducted on the Wakayama, Japan [61] on the forest canopy consisting of Japanese cedar showing with dual frequency receiver showing the positioning accuracy value of 3.26 m. Similarly, survey done on Norway [70] on the forest consisting of Norway spruce, Scots pine and Birch trees with the single frequency receiver showing RMSE value of 2.7 m.

5.5. Current state-of-the-art articles often provide recommendations for managing variations in positioning accuracy.

The common articles reveals that multiple factors influence accuracy variation between the forest canopy and the open sky [60], Likely other research demonstrated that open-sky navigation has higher positional accuracy due to reduced signal interferences [9], less multipath, and higher satellite visibility [49]. The other associated conditions that influence accuracy are leaves off periods, sparse vegetation, and forest stands, which are directly related to fewer positional errors, prefer proper positioning, and provide better geometry. The proposed solutions most authors from reviewed papers that are contributing to changing accuracy apart from the seasonal differences in GNSS positioning are.

- i) Atmospheric influences [80]
- ii) Multipath effects related to environmental changes [74]

- iii) Satellite geometry and seasonal positioning [46]
- iv) Geophysical variations influencing GNSS measurements [11, 81]
- v) Interference and noise impacting signal quality [82]
- vi) Receiver performance variation [78]
- vii) Receiver and antenna calibration due to seasonal dynamics [79]

The other factors that affect GNSS's accuracy despite technological advancements are location and its geography structure, along with associated features, which can make forest navigation challenging. Additionally, the instability of positioning devices may not fully support the desired level of accuracy in GNSS positioning. Geographical features can significantly influence GNSS accuracy at the micro level [83], urban environments and their GNSS settings, distance from local reference stations, and the availability of base stations.

Summary on most effective correction approaches evaluated from selected journals.

A review of numerous journal articles highlights effective techniques for improving GNSS positioning accuracy from the multiple surveys of collected publications with different ranges of horizontal accuracy from meters to centimeters level. The analysis capacity of RTK approaches [52, 65, 71, 74] to produce high horizontal accuracy in real-time shows the most popular techniques on GNSS navigation. In the same way, article VI highlights that by mounting the height of the receiver, the desired level of accuracy can be maintained; in the same way, article XIX mentions that PPP techniques can be used for observation time during the data gathering to increase accuracy, whereas [9], highlights PPP independence in producing accurate results. Regarding the search for another approach, article XII demonstrates the integration of pseudo-range and carrier phase measurement along with receiver antenna height adjustment, enhancing positioning reliability. Similarly, (articles II,XXV,XV) emphasized the post-processed differential correction using a mapping grade receiver, and the accuracy level was enhanced. Regarding augmentation techniques applied in several research studies, they were found in a broad range of real-time RTK methods, standalone with single point positioning and differential GNSS. On close observation, a multi-constellation GNSS system was noticed, and an innovative approach to hemispheric images to capture pertinent data was utilized. Similarly, post-processing techniques,

especially RTK, DGNSS and PPP, were utilized after data gathering and applied for positioning correction. Finally, journals utilize the post-processing tool from ASG EUPOS, which significantly enhances GNSS positioning accuracy by optimizing network density during the surveys.

5.6. Contrast on applied techniques used assessing the current state of the art.

The most popular technique (DGPS) was applied to improve signal consistency by utilizing reference stations that provide real-time error corrections. On the other hand, extending observation time was observed parallelly to increase accuracy by gathering and averaging data over longer intervals. In some studies, raising the antenna height reduces signal obstructions in the middle of the forest, and it was observed that it enhances precision in cluttered environments. Moreover, examining the leaf-on and leaf-off stages in trees or forest areas highlighted the influence of vegetation on signal propagation. Lastly, fine-tuning the receiver settings for optimized performance ensures hardware configurations effectively address environmental factors and specific application needs.

5.7. Current state of the ort- multipath mitigation techniques

A multipath error occurs when GNSS satellite signals reflect off from surfaces such as trees, terrain, or dense canopies, which creates interference and distorts the original phase by fluctuation in a carrier. Two-phase variations of multipath effects can be observed, one with multipath with no carrier phase where the receiver receiving signals has minimal or no reflection resulting in a clear and accurate phase measurement where the transmission remains generally intact and without interference-free whereas on the other side, the receiver encounter substantial interferences as huge phase changes, where maximum carrier phase multipath effect takes place, which can be further classified as destructive and constructive phases [38]. The reflected signals can align in phase with the direct signal for constructive interferences, boosting overall signal strength. However, this alignment may also introduce inaccuracies in phase measurements. In contrast, for destructive interferences, the reflected signals can combine out of phase with the direct signal, leading to a weakening or distortion

of the signal. This destructive interference results in greater measurement errors, as significant phase variations make it challenging for the receiver to determine the correct phase accurately [25, 84].

This review summarizes articles that explore alleviation techniques on the multipath using various strategies, such as choke ring antennas, multi-constellation GNSS, and hemispheric photography, which are most used in the forest environment.

5.8. Multipath mitigation techniques using hardware solutions.

For multi-path mitigation, the hardware components are used; they are categorized based on receiver configuration and antenna design. For any GNSS receiver, various models are designed to sort, rectify, and make corrections on multipath effects, whereas an antenna possesses the ability to hinder, deny, and diminish the multipath signals during signal processing [59]. From the numerous studies, several types of receiver categorization were found that were working on multipath lessening effect, where plentiful of receivers were designed for dual frequency or multi-channel frequency to distinguish multipath frequency and real signal where they have ability to filter signal by modifying by use of adaptive filtering methods that can dynamically modify filter parameters according to the multipath conditions at any given time, lowering errors instantly as well as utilizing the loop which is delay loop to separate multipath from the main signals [63]. While considering antenna part on the recent technological development, multiple category of antennas are developed based on the hardware setup where applied techniques like optimizing antenna gain pattern for maximization of the gaining of the signals coming from satellite the higher horizontal elevation for robust positioning, another techniques applied so-called Right hand circular polarization (RHCP) from the antenna designed creating antenna high sensitivities to right hand side, consider the fact that of changing reflection frequency to left-hand side and so that signal from left side are discarded, other strategy found on the ground plane antennas of GNSS receiver where ground planes acting as a natural barrier for decreasing multipath by reflecting undesired low angle signals [38].

5.9. Hemispheric photographic technology

It is one of the techniques used for multipath reduction, where complete photography is taken in forest areas, especially canopy, sky, and surroundings, using a fish-eye lens of the camera near the GNSS receiver to generate a map of obstacles. They help to identify obstructions (e.g., trees, branches, and overall forest territory) that block and find potential sources that reflect satellite signals; they create interference to avoid GNSS signals [59, 85]. Numerous studies have suggested that integrating and applying these techniques with signal filtering and sky masking can significantly enhance the accuracy and reliability of GNSS positioning on the challenging of the landscapes. This technique assists in receiver and antenna for the possible adjustment for lessening the multipath on the GNSS in the forest settings [59].

5.10. Multi-constellations GNSS

Utilizing the multi-constellation on GNSS means leveraging several satellite systems, including GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, and BeiDou. In environments such as forests, multipath effects—where signals reflect off surfaces before reaching the receiver—are inevitable (as discussed in articles XXI and IX). However, by incorporating signals from various constellations and GNSS receivers, the number of visible satellites increases, which enhances satellite geometry and mitigates the impact of multipath errors. As the research findings from article XIV indicate, numerous studies emphasize the effectiveness and practicality of multi-constellation systems for positioning corrections. Multi-constellation receivers exhibit greater resilience against signal blockages caused by trees and uneven terrain. Overall, multi-constellation GNSS is highly effective in alleviating multipath errors by improving satellite visibility.

Choke ring antenna.

Multiple studies carried out on field campaigns claims that the effectiveness of choke ring antennas reduces multipath errors by improving accuracy [59]. There are several antennas designed for the multipath , especially in environments where reflected signals are prevalent, such as forested and urban areas [26].From article IX, showing the effectivity on the

application of choke ring device by comparing two different antennas Beacon and Choke ring. During the analysis of multipath mitigation, the application of the choke ring on horizontal positional accuracy after DPGS corrected was found on the range between 0.32 m to 0.88 m on the forest, with leaf-bearing stage and on leaf off period records shows 0.35 m to 0.69 m positional accuracy where on the same survey beacon antenna showing horizontal accuracy on the range of 4.9 m to 6.1 on the leaf off stage where as on the leaf on period showing 3.3 m to 5.8 m positional accuracy on the forest zone where multipath was prevalent.

Broad view on fixation of multipath through choke ring antenna

Approach with choke ring antenna for multipath reduction, as discussed in several studies shows that receiver and its antenna design on the hardware part are the major component that can enhance positioning and navigation in the forest location. The authors from [42], explains the Choke ring antenna design and its working functionalities where from article IV, article XXI and supports from article XXIII, the use of this antenna in the vegetation zone, similarly authors [59] and author [85] strongly support the view regarding choke ring, with a focus on improvements in positioning techniques in the forest environment; as possible solution that can be taken as modern technical on the state of art [85]. During the navigation of GNSS on any type of geographical location of forests, where the forest stands acting as a hurdle for signal blockage and the environment inside of the forest canopy on windy conditions, where moving canopy components accelerate chances for multi-path effects [8]. Considering the design and configuration, the antenna has multiple concentric rings that help to filter incoming signals and that are used effectively for error reduction. They are designed for selective signal reception techniques, helping to isolate direct signals from satellites, where the reflected signals [63], reducing signal interference by filtering out reflected signals and maintaining horizontal location accuracy. The improved signal-to-noise ratio indicates a clearer signal for accurate GPS readings. Additional factors like stability and precision are enhanced by dependable signal record on and multipath effect errors [59]. For Wideband Performance, having the ability to pick up signals from multiple satellite signals [85]. Considering all those characteristics from several authors mentioned multipath that

present abundantly present in the forest canopy, a conceivable way to reduce by choke antenna.

Figure 15: Three-dimensional choke ring GNSS antenna [17]

CHAPTER 5

6. Discussion /Synthesis

6.1. GNSS positioning in forests “a synthesis on current methods and accuracy.”

From the several research studies and examination techniques have shown that using a standalone GNSS receiver may not provide the desired level of accuracy for navigation and mapping in forested areas [1]. However, accuracy and precision can be improved to a certain level, from meter to centimeter scale, through various augmentation techniques. The numerous research studies on GNSS positioning within the forested region provide sufficient indication that multiple challenges are encountered for satellite wave signals and provides a brief understanding about signal degradation, various obstructing agents like multipath interferences and positional obstructions. Those major concerns issue primarily arises from multiple factors, like canopy density, topography, terrain or slope and forest structure [10]. Addressed had made from other studies by utilization of high precision geodetic receivers,

survey-grade receivers, mapping grade, and autonomous receiver tools form popular hardware devices like Topcon Hiper GGS, Stonex S900A and other popular tools like AshTech and Leica, which were frequently used in forestry surveys [73]. Along with receiver augmentation with DGPS techniques are used for those weak, noise signals that were showing inconsistency during the positioning operation. Similarly, advanced multi-level GNSS constellations were used on numerous surveys [67], showing satisfying results for the deduction of certain levels of noise and amplifying and filtering the signal [63]. However, the results were not similar because of variations in tree age and species diversity [70].

For the accuracy part, antenna height was increased for mitigation of multipath [57]. As there was a heterogeneous mixture of papers representing the mapping by GNSS on the entire globe, providing the core message to the reader about GNSS encountering several challenges during the navigation on the forest in the presence of the dense canopy, where signal blockages, attenuation, multipath, and less satellite visibility are the common issues. Because of the underlying issue, positioning error is a great challenge. From the collected research journals clarify that they are with the slight changes on the canopy density, with the remarkable changes on the positional accuracies (articles XV, VII, XII). Similarly, seasonal changes and leaf on period dramatically increase the more errors in the articles (IV, V) creating more challenges on the navigation. With the support of GNSS constellation like (GPS, GNSS, Beidou and other additional regional satellites), the satellite visibility chances are increased, lowering DOP values and accuracy promoting. On the same time, with the use of augmentation techniques like RTK, PPP and DGPS, the promising level of accuracy as much as 0.03 m can be obtained (article XXII). On the same time, utilization of various models of GNSS receiver certain level of positioning error can be decrease. However, all those techniques might not work well in the forest setting because of the availability of multipath, for addressing this issue choke ring antenna and hemispherical photography was applied (articles, XV). Despite those all-applied techniques there seems to be a critical research gap in the current study and shows interest in further research on multiple fields. The current study focuses on the study on the general forest which is not defined or all types of forests that consists of various types of forests mainly broadleaves, coniferous and mixed

on the climatic zone temperate, tropical, plain and mountainous regions. Despite those techniques multiple questions were raised on the GNSS positioning on the forest. In the study multiple things had been mentioned like multipath mitigation techniques, its robust approach, implementation, and its effectiveness on forest. Similarly, inconsistency regarding partial and changing forest canopy and signaling approach with combination processing methodology, similarly the non-canopy factors atmospheric conditions as well as ionospheric effect were poorly comprehended (article XVI). As GNSS service was used on the moving forest for multiple operations like logging operations and vehicle transportation (article XVII) where continuous monitoring and explorations must be addressed to boost navigation operation in motion and its efficiency. For further studies, during the research, versatile strategy should be followed to make link to theoretical advancements with real life application to address those gaps on the broad range of forest types and geographical terrains, which is crucial aspect for improving the result. Additionally, it is important to create and validate signal processing methods in forest setting mode that would create a bridge in forestry operations and various navigations by GNSS.

6.2. Hardware receiver settings on the current state-of-the-art used on positioning techniques.

Each peer review paper describes applied hardware techniques used during the experiments. From the provided varied objectives and methodologies, the review reveals broad categories of several types of GPS receiver models, each having distinct configurations and settings levels. As **Appendix II** provides a collection of a comprehensive list of all individual receivers referenced across those studies. The most used receivers in GNSS field positioning on the forest location are Topcon Hiper GGD, Leica SR530, Trimble Pathfinder Pro XR, Trimble Geo XH, Stoney S900A, Javad Legacy, Trimble R8 GNSS, Leica Viva GNSS, Ashtech Surveying GPS, Gramin Receiver, Visontec VGPS 900, Trimble GeoXH6000, Javad Triumph 1. The analysis found that receiver survey-grade received claimed accuracy on the centimeter scale. Geodetic-grade receivers exhibit exceptional sensitivity and robustness, particularly in achieving centimeter-level accuracy through Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) positioning. The next most frequently mentioned type in peer-reviewed

studies is the mapping-grade receiver, which employs a dual-frequency GNSS system. These receivers are widely utilized for positioning tasks and can attain accuracy within the meter to centimeters range. Lastly, consumer-level receivers are recognized for providing positional accuracy at the meter level.

Figure 16: Receivers used in correction techniques literature resources.

The goal of upcoming research is to improve GNSS positioning accuracy and to provide a clear understanding of its influencing factors in the forest regions.

Although GNSS navigation is applied to various forest locations with varying landscapes, forest types, geographical features, and different types of forest environments with unique tree species types, the differences of canopy and foliage cover present absolute challenges to accurate positions due to the vastness of forest structure, multipath effects and interruption of the signals. The lack of forest-specific GNSS positioning methods indicates a gap in research focused on adaptive and environmentally responsive GNSS systems. Several studies have clarified that open environments may perform better from standard GNSS settings. However, forest dynamic solutions are influenced by factors like tree height, species variety,

canopy covers, leaf features, weather conditions, and positioning device models, which introduce a complex set of variables that are extremely hard to predict.

Future research is needed to improve methodology, algorithms, and conceptual models to boost efficiency and accuracy.

Accuracy in Dense Canopies: GNSS signal accuracy significantly decreases in areas with dense canopies due to issues like multipath effects and reduced visibility.

Articles (I, III, V, VIII, X, XII, XXI)

Effect of Seasonal and Environmental Variables: Changes in foliage with the seasons, different tree species, types of terrain, humidity, and ionospheric variations impact GNSS accuracy.

Articles (IV, X, XI, XVI)

PDOP and Satellite Availability: Elevated PDOP values in forested environments compromise positioning accuracy, with GLONASS typically performing poorer than GPS.

(Articles II, VII, XV, XXIII)

Real-Time and Rapid Data Collection: Achieving quick positioning in dynamic settings (like vehicles moving through forests) presents accurate challenges.

Articles (VIII, XVII, XVIII)

Differential GPS and RTK for Forest Use: While DGPS and RTK can enhance accuracy, they encounter performance limitations in obstructed areas.

Articles (III, XII, XIV, XIX, XXV).

6.3. Improving Equipment and Practical Implementation

Optimized Hardware Design: Standard configurations of GNSS receivers, antennas, and poles frequently for further performance in forested locations.

Articles (VI, IX, XIII)

Affordable and Accessible GNSS Technology: High-precision GNSS systems are often expensive, and more budget-friendly options tend to sacrifice accuracy.

Articles (XIV, XVIII, XXV)

Figure 17: Example of various accuracy mentioned from the selected literature resources.

6.4. Various applications of GNSS in the current state in forestry

GNSS provides information based on positioning, velocity, and time (PVT). It's usability can be found in diverse range of application and services field like weather, environmental monitoring, agro-forestry, agriculture, surveying as well as in the farming [86]. While considering about its application on the forestry area, and forest related sector like forest

monitoring, mapping, logging and associate category. Those practices are applied with different techniques, hardware setup and with the main purpose of getting desirable accuracy along with high amount of precision. In current practices, the foresters aim to know information related to trees and their components like single tree measurements, height measurement, canopy wide measurement along with diameter breast height (DBH) of the trees [52]. It is very crucial to know such attributes because inaccuracies in positioning techniques can lead to multiple errors, which can be a problem for the forest itself as well as forest management. Those faults lead to an increase in inventory management, which includes loss of time, work, money, and resources. One of the regular use services on forestry is forest thinning or cutting trees in the silviculture operation where a scientific forest management is practiced for the restoration ,an agile, healthier forest and forest related activities which are carried out on dense forest stand and in the forest canopy where trees are fell down for purpose of feed stock expansion , bio based products and production as well as in forest restoration for forest safety and protection [87].In the thinning process initially survey of forest is carried out where spatial scanning is done with the help of navigation satellite or devices for georeferencing and proper execution of the work [52]. For every tree stand, accuracy is very mandatory so as the precision, which is connected to concerning for several activities as aforementioned. The major activities happening in silviculture area for forest management, inventory management, mapping of a forest, tree planting activities, and canopy measurement which are used in day to day life [10]. One of the other frequently used application on forest is route planning inside the dense forest canopy, where emergency route are constructed for recovery and support especially for off road transport optimization in search operation, by military or rescue worker where observation posts, army bases, storage are maintained and optimized with the help of coordinate system on the unknown location by application of multi-constellation of GNSS system or optimization of the augmentation system [88]. For forest applications operation of navigation, multiple range of receiver are used whereas forest related harvesting associated equipment's are used so called A- GPS [41], digital forestry that include various smart navigation like smart phones or smart watch both consisting sensors which operates with GNSS Radio frequency in the precision forestry [89] .Likely on the regular forest practice with the application of navigation

machinery like LIDAR and UAVS arial survey are conducted that are supported with GNSS technology where tree inventory mapping and laser analysis can be done in minute scale [90]. With the support of augmentation techniques like RTK and DGNSS as well as PPP meters to centimeters level of positioning accuracy has been obtained on the forestry sector for precision scale in the field of yielding, tree harvesting that create certain level of productivity boost to whole forestry sector.

7. Conclusion

This project focuses on understanding the positioning approach of satellite monitoring systems, focusing on the GNSS constellation, from satellite navigation to receiver device signaling techniques, types of error from satellites and receiver perspective, and the correction techniques used to process accuracy correction during satellite monitoring in the forest. During the comparison, several literature correction techniques were used in forested environments alongside the most advanced methods, such as RTK, DGPS, and PPP techniques, which were used for data correction in the forest covered with a dense canopy. The analysis revealed that both RTK and DGPS error correction techniques delivered satisfactory results that achieved centimeter-level accuracy in the field surveys. For the enhancement of GNSS positioning, dual frequency receivers were most used, and for the best accuracy receiver that supports a continuous Auspos network in RTK in both static and kinetic mode, for the most effective approach, multi-frequency and multi-constellation tech are recommended. Antenna height and precise point position also provided centimeter-level accuracy in other cases. One major limitation of this research is that it examines peer-reviewed publications based on various survey reports that utilize different survey concepts. The review indicates that most studies were conducted over a decade ago and relied on outdated techniques and equipment. In contrast, recent technological advancements have produced promising results in GNSS positioning within forest environments. Only a few studies in the past five years have demonstrated centimeter-level accuracy. To ensure a

thorough analysis, it is essential to use precise data and modern correction technologies, as these can significantly improve precision and accuracy in forest mapping using GNSS.

8. APPENDICES I

Article Number	Name of the Journal Article with Digital Identification Number
I	Assessing horizontal accuracy of inventory plots in forests with different mixes of tree species composition and development stage, DOI:10.17221/92/2018-JFS
II	Accuracy and Precision of GPS Receivers under forest canopies in a mountainous environment, DOI:10.5424/sjar/2010084-1242
III	Comparing the precision and accuracy of GPS Positioning in Forested Areas, DOI:10.1007/s10310-002-0020-0
IV	Impact of Forest Spatial Structure on variation of the Multipath phenomenon of navigation satellite signals, DOI:10.2478/ffp-2019-001
V	Impact of forest canopy on quality and accuracy of GPS Measurements, DOI:10.1080/014311699211228
VI	The Effect of Mounting Height on GNSS Receiver Accuracy in Forest Conditions, ISSN-1845-5719
VII	Tree Location Measurement Accuracy with a Mapping-Grade GPS receiver under Forest Canopy, DOI:10.5849/forsci.11-015
VIII	Rapid Static Positioning Using a Four System GNSS receiver in the Forest Environment, DOI :10.3390/f13010045
IX	Multipath Mitigation under Forest Canopies: A Choke Ring Antenna Solution, DOI:10.1093/forestscience/55.2.109
X	Effects of Canopy and Multi-Epoch Observation on Single Point Positioning Errors of a GNSS in Coniferous and Broadleaved Forest, DOI:10.3390/rs13122325
XI	Horizontal Accuracy and applicability of smartphone GNSS positioning in forests, DOI:10.1093/forestry/cpw031

XII	Point Accuracy of combined pseudo-range and carrier phase differential GPS under Forest canopy, DOI:10.1139/x99-021
XIII	Analysis of GNSS Receiver Accuracy in the forest environment, DOI:
XIV	Low-Cost GNSS receiver RTK Performance in forest environment, DOI: 10.23919/URSIRCRS49211.2020.9113621
XV	Behavior of GPS signal Interruption Probability under Tree Canopies in Different Forest Conditions; DOI:10.5721/EuJRS20134636
XVI	Seasonal Variation of GPS Accuracy and Precision in Forest Road Mapping, DOI: 10.31926/but.fwiafe.2022.15.64.1.1
XVII	Balancing Horizontal Accuracy and Data Collection Efficiency with mapping - grade GPS receivers, DOI: 10.1093/forestry/cpt054
XVIII	Evaluating Global Positioning System Accuracy for Forest Biomass Transportation Tracking within Varying Forest Canopy, DOI :10.1093/wjaf/26.4.165
XIX	Performance of GPS Precise Point Positioning Under Conifer Forest Canopies, DOI:10.14358/PERS.74.5.661
XX	Effect of occupation time on the horizontal accuracy of a mapping-grade GNSS receiver under dense forest canopy, DOI: 10.14358/PERS.83.12.861
XXI	The effects of nearby trees on the positional accuracy of GNSS receiver in a forest environment, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0283090
XXII	Reliable Technology of Centimeter GPS/GLONASS Surveying in Forest Environments, DOI :10.1109/TGRS.2014.2332372
XXIII	Assessment of the GNSS-RTK for Application in Precision Forest Operations, DOI: 10.3390/rs16010148
XIV	The seasonal effects of Deciduous tree foliage in CORS -GNSS Measurement (VRS/FKP), DOI: 10.17559/TV-20150301214046
XXV	Horizontal Measurement Performance of Five Mapping Grade Global Positioning System Receiver Configuration in Several Forested Settings, DOI:10.1093/wjaf/23.3.166

Table 4: 25 -Articles on GNSS on forest mapping listed on accuracy table.

Article number	Title name of Journal Article with DOI
1.1	Positioning Methods and the use of location and Activity Data in forests, DOI:10.3390/f10050458
1.2	A review on Multi – GNSS for Earth Observation and Emerging Applications, DOI:10.3390/rs14163930
1.3	Keeping Pace with Global Positioning System Technology in the Forest, DOI:10.1093/jof/106.6.332
1.4	Accuracy of Kinematic Positioning Using Global Satellite Navigation Systems Under Forest Canopies, DOI: 10.3390/f6093218
1.5	Assessment Of the GNSS -RTK for Application in Precision Forest operations, DOI:10.3390/rs16010148
1.6	Quantitative Evaluation of GPS performance under forest Canopies, DOI:10.1109/ICNSC.2005.1461289
1.7	Influences of Global Navigation Satellite System errors in positioning inventory plots for tree -height distributions studies, DOI: 10.1139/X10-164
1.8	GNSS Signal Quality in Forest Stands for Off-Road Vehicle Navigation, DOI:10.3390/app13106142
1.9	On Mitigation of the Effects of Multipath on GNSS Using Environmental Context Detection, DOI:10.3390/app122312389
2.0	Remote Sensing in Forestry: current challenges, considerations and directions, DOI:10.1093/forestry/cpad024
2.1	Unlocking Digitalization in Forest Operations with viewshed Analysis to Improve GNSS Positioning Accuracy, DOI:10.3390/f14040689

2.2	Performance Accuracy of Real- Time GPS Asset Tracking Systems for Timber Haulage Travelling Trucks on Both internal Forest Roads and Public Road Networks, DOI:10.1080/14942119.2009.10702575
2.3	Performance of RTK Positioning in Forest Conditions: Case Study, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9453(2009)135:3(125)
2.4	Consumer -Grade GPS Receiver Measurement Accuracy In varying Forest Conditions, DOI:10.3923/rjf.2011.78.88
2.5	Accurate single-tree positioning from a harvester: a test of two global satellites -based positioning systems, DOI:10.1080/02827581.2017.1296967
2.6	GNSS use in forestry -A multinational survey from Iran, Slovakia and southern USA, DOI: 10.1016/j.compag.2019.02.015
2.7	Application of Real-time Positioning Systems to a Forest Stand for Precision Forest management, DOI:10.18494/SAM4214
2.8	Unlocking Digitalization in forest Operations with Viewshed Analysis to Improve GNSS Positioning Accuracy, DOI:10.3390/f14040689
2.9	Global Positioning System and Forest Applications, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8057706
3.0	GNSS in Precision Agriculture Operations, DOI:10.5772/50448
3.1	GNSS -based operational monitoring devices for forest logging operation chains, DOI:10.4081/jae.2013.269
3.2	Use of Real -Time GNSS-RF Data to Characterize the Swing Movements of Forestry Equipment, DOI:10.3390/f8020044
3.3	Development and Testing of a New UWB Positioning Measurement Tool to Assist in Forest Surveys, DOI:10.3390/su142417042
3.4	Application research of satellite-ground positioning technology in forestry, DOI: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.530-531.715
3.5	Application and Development at Home of Geographical Information System in Forestry Resource, DOI:10.2991/icsmim-15.2016.192

Table 5: List of associates 25 -articles based on GNSS positioning **not listed** on accuracy table includes title and with DOI.

8.1. APPENDICES II

List Of Hardware GNSS Receivers

Journal Serial Number	Article Reference	Receiver Name	Manufacturer	GNSS Supported	Frequency Bands	Special Features	Other Equipment Used
1	[81]	Topcon Hiper GGD, Topcon FC -25 A	Topcon	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency	High precision	
2	[11]	Lecia GS50, SR530, Topcon Hiper Pro, GMS2	Leica, Topcon	GPS	Dual frequency	Combined with Total Station	
3	[61]	Trimble Pathfinder Pro XR	Trimble	GPS	Single frequency	Rover GNSS Receiver	
4	[10]	Trimble R8 GNSS, Stonex S9, Topcon Hiper Pro, Lecia Viva GS08 Plus	Trimble, Stonex, Leica	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency	Independence of Exchange System	
5	[49]	Ashtech Surveying Grade GPS, Trimble Pro XL	Ashtech, Trimble	GPS	Single frequency	cm-level accuracy, Pseudo-range receiver	Community Base Station
6	[57]	Topcon Hiper Pro	Topcon	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency	Geodetic grade	-

7	[60]	Trimble GeoXH, Trimble Pro XH	Trimble	GPS	Single frequency	External Antenna	-
8	[73]	Stonex S900A, CHC LT700H	Stonex, CHC	GPS, GLONASS, Galileo, BeiDou	Dual frequency	Geodetic-class, GIS-class receiver	-
9	[63]	Trimble ProXR	Trimble	GPS	Single frequency	-	-
10	[74]	Galaxy 6 RTK GNSS	-	GPS	Dual frequency	RTK (Real-Time Kinematic)	Total Station
11	[75]	Trimble Nomad	Trimble	GPS	Single frequency		Total Station Theodolite
12	[70]	Trimble Geo Explorer I, Pathfinder ProXR, Ashtech Super C/A	Trimble, Ashtech	GPS	Single frequency	12-channel receiver	
13	[51]	GNSS Receivers	Topcon HiperPro	GPS	Dual frequency	General mention	
14	[67]	Satellite Receiver		GPS		General mention	
15	[76]	Leica GPS SR530, Trimble GPS Total Station	Leica, Trimble	GPS	Dual frequency		
16	[77]	Colorado 300		GPS	Single frequency		
17	[78]	Mapping Grade Receiver		GPS			

18	[1]	Topcon Hiper GGD, Topcon FC-25A	Topcon	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency	Leaf-off season usage	Field Controller
19	[56]	Vision tac VGPS 900	Vision tac	GPS			
20	[9]	Javad Legacy	Javad	GPS	Dual frequency	Pseudo-range & carrier phase	
21	[64]	Trimble GeoXH 6000, Javad Triumph	Trimble, Javad	GPS	Dual frequency		
22	[65]	Garmin receiver, Trimble receiver, Ashtech Locus Survey Grade	Garmin, Trimble, Ashtech	GPS		Survey grade	Smartphone
23	[85]	Trimble R12i	Trimble	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency	Trimble R12i	Lidar sensor
24	[71]	Topcon Hiper Pro GNSS, 3- Ashtech Z Max	Topcon	GPS GLONASS	+Dual frequency		
25	[80]	Trimble Geo XH	Trimble	GPS	Single frequency	Auto	

Table 6: Various receivers used for accurate positioning.

Figure 17 : Hardware setup available on current state of art

Unlocking the Potential of GNSS Positioning Receiver - Systematic Workflow for Error Correction

Figure 19: Accuracy enhancement techniques in real-time or post-processing

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8.1.3 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full Form
GPS	Global Positioning System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GLONASS	Globalnaya Navigazionnaya Sputnikovaya
BDS	BeiDou Navigation Satellite System
IOV	In orbit Validation
SPS	Standard Positioning Service
GEO	Geosynchronous Earth Orbit
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
PRN	Pseudo Random Noise
RF	Radio Frequency
C/A	Coarse/Acquisition Code
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter

AGC	Automatic Gain Control
CDMA	Code Division Multiple Access
DBH	Density Breadth Height
DLL	Delay Lock Loop (DLL)
HDOP	Horizontal Dilution of Precision
VDOP	Vertical Dilution of Precision
TDOP	Time Dilution of Precision
GDOP	Geometric Dilution of Precision
NaVIC	Navigation with Indian Constellations,
GSO	Geostationary Orbit,
IGSO	Inclined Geostationary Orbit
DGNSS	Differential GNSS
RTK	Real -Time Kinematics
WAAS	Wide Area Augmentation System
SBAS	Space Base Augmentation System
EGNOS	European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service
QZSS	Quasi-Zenith Satellite System
PPP-	Precise Point Positioning

CORS	Continuously Operating Reference Station
VRS –	Virtual Reference Station
RTK –	Real-Time Kinematics
FKP-	Flächen Korrektur Parameter
ASG-EUPOS	Active Geodetic Network European Position Determination System
ADC	Analog to digital converter
DSC	Digital signal processor
DOI	Digital Object Identifier

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